

OPEN REPOSITORIES CONFERENCE 2024

The International Conference on Open Repositories
3 - 6 June 2024 | Gothenburg, Sweden

Conference Agenda

Session Overview

Date: Monday, 03/June/2024

08:30 - 16:00	Registration Location: Built Environment I-II / Samhällsbyggnad I-II
09:30 - 12:30	Workshop 1 Location: SB-M022 Session Chair: Urban Andersson , Chalmers University of Technology
	ID: 293 / W10: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Research projects, Persistent identifiers, transparency, collaboration Research Activity Identifiers (RaiDs): Opening the 'black box' of project information Shawn Adrian Ross , Siobhann McCafferty , Natasha Simons Australian Research Data Commons, Australia
09:30 - 12:30	Workshop 3 Location: SB-M415 Session Chair: Elizabeth Krznrach , DataCite
	ID: 133 / W03: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), DSpace, DSpace-CRIS, Persistent Identifiers, Metadata Creating DOIs with rich metadata using DSpace Kelly Stathis ¹ , Pascal-Nicolas Becker ² , Andrea Bollini ³ , Claudio Cortese ³ , Jordan Piščanc ³ , Sheila Rabun ⁴ ¹ DataCite; ² The Library Code GmbH; ³ Science; ⁴ Lyrasis In this workshop, DSpace administrators will learn how to enable, configure, and maximize the benefits of the DSpace 7 DataCite DOI integration. Workshop facilitators will cover the DataCite DOI registration process, the DataCite Metadata Schema, configuration options within DSpace and DSpace-CRIS, and how to customize the metadata mapping between local repository metadata and the DataCite Metadata Schema.
09:30 - 12:30	Workshop 2 Location: SB3-L111 Session Chair: Ilkay Holt , British Library
	ID: 402 / W12: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems <i>Keywords:</i> wcag, accessibility, accessible repositories, pdf Unlocking Accessibility: PDF Annotation with PDF/UA Standard and WCAG Guidelines Łukasz Kobylński , Łukasz Skonieczny , Agata Drozd , Antoni Marek , Jakub Koperwas Sages, Poland
09:30 - 12:30	Workshop 4 Location: SB3-L112 Session Chair: Emily Bongiovanni , Carnegie Mellon University
	ID: 144 / W09: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> APIs, open science, research lifecycle, research insights, reporting, statistics OSF Search API for Research Transparency and Discovery Gretchen Mary Gueguen , Futa Ikeda Center for Open Science, United States of America The Open Science Framework (OSF) is a platform that supports the research process through data repository services, scientific study registration, and preprint publishing. This workshop will feature a hands-on tutorial on creating queries for the new OSF Search API and parsing results. With the new API users can extract useful information to glean valuable insights into research activities on OSF. Two types of OSF Search API queries will be taught and attendees will be able to form their own queries using the Search API parameters. Typical use cases will be reviewed and attendees will be able to practice queries using the live API during the session. By the end of this workshop data librarians, repository managers, research support staff and repository developers will be able to use the OSF Search API to gather data for reports or other applications.
09:30 - 17:00	Workshop 6 Location: SB-M500 Session Chair: Nora Mulvaney , Toronto Metropolitan University
	ID: 107 / W01: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Reproducible research, FAIR, equity, scholarly communication, credit, collaboration, InvenioRDM, research data management, metrics InvenioRDM Workshop 2024 Alex Ioannidis ¹ , Karolina Przewa ¹ , Thomas Morrell ² , Dan Granville ³ , Martin Fenner ⁴ , Ekaterina Pechekhonova ⁵ , Deb Verhoff ⁵ , Matthew B. Carson ⁶ , Sara Gonzales ⁶ , Guillaume Viger ⁶ , Kristi L. Holmes ⁶ , Maximilian Moser ⁷ , Sotirios Tsepelakis ⁷ , Michael Groh ⁸ , Karl Krägelin ⁹ , Sarah Wiechers ⁹

	<p>¹European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), Geneva, Switzerland; ²California Institute of Technology, United States of America; ³Data Futures; ⁴Front Matter; ⁵New York University, United States of America; ⁶Northwestern University, Feinberg School of Medicine, Gatter Health Sciences Library & Learning Center, United States of America; ⁷Technische Universität Wien, Vienna, Austria; ⁸University of Bamberg, Bamberg, Germany; ⁹Universität Münster, Münster, Germany</p> <p>InvenioRDM is a next-generation, turnkey repository and research data management platform supporting FAIR practices, research transparency, and discovery of a wide range of research outputs. Serving as both the new back-end of Zenodo.org and a standalone institutional repository solution, InvenioRDM supports research communities, data sharing and availability compliance, and researcher credit by employing a robust and widely-adopted metadata standard, powerful search features, and ORCID- and ROR-enhanced creator and contributor fields. This InvenioRDM workshop will provide repository managers, developers, system/software administrators, decision makers, and librarians the opportunity to familiarize themselves with both the open source repository framework and the active community that supports it. This full-day workshop will feature opportunities for hands-on installation work for developers, as well as presentations on local customizations and community-benefiting software enhancements, and opportunities for interactive discussion. Throughout the day, we will increase participants' knowledge about the InvenioRDM framework and about how to become involved in this dynamic community. InvenioRDM's strong multi-national collaboration of academic, research, funding, and industry partners from Europe, Asia, Africa, and North America is eager to share with new collaborators the ways in which it can work with them to increase transparency, provide visibility to all researchers, and support sustainability.</p>
09:30 - 17:00	<p>Workshop 7 Location: SB3-L113 Session Chair: Jessica Lindholm, Chalmers University of Technology</p>
	<p>ID: 227 / W02: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> static sites, repository development</p> <p>Super - Simple - Static - Sustainable: a low resource repository jam Peter Sefton¹, Kim Shepherd², John Salter³, Claire Knowles³ ¹University of Queensland; ²The Library Code GmbH; ³University of Leeds</p> <p>Inspired by Prof Hussein Suleman's closing keynote at OR2023 "Designing Repositories in Poor Countries" this workshop will explore practical implementations of Suleman's principles and goals. We will encourage developers, metadata specialists and managers to embrace, simple and sustainable approaches to making data safe and available using well established static web publishing techniques with on-demand indexes and discovery interfaces – contrasting with the complexity of current repository stacks which have grown into bloated enterprise software where setup and data migration are very expensive and hosting requirements are substantial. We will explore a range of technologies including those mentioned in the keynote and encourage people to join teams that take them away from the large, complex vertically integrated systems that many of us work in day to day. We aim to have participants work (in a sustainable way) on their ideas and present them in a special developer stream on the final day, and for us all to report back on what we learned at the closing keynote and to talk about possibilities for progressing the ideas we explored during the workshop and OR 2024.</p>
12:30 - 14:00	Lunch time
14:00 - 15:30	<p>Workshop 8 Location: SB-M022 Session Chair: Katarina Wiberg, National Library of Sweden</p>
	<p>ID: 165 / W06: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> persistent identifiers, metadata, preservation, curation, permalinks</p> <p>Getting running with ARK persistent identifiers John Andrew Kunze¹, Donny Winston² ¹College of Computing and Informatics, Drexel University, United States of America; ²Polyneme LLC</p> <p>In this 90-minute tutorial we will introduce you to ARKs (Archival Resource Keys), which can serve as persistent identifiers, or stable, trusted references for information objects (eg, web addresses that don't return 404 Page Not Found errors). In more than two decades, 8.2 billion ARKs have been created by over 1200 organizations — libraries, data centers, archives, museums, publishers, government agencies, and vendors. Highly flexible and non-paywalled, ARKs are adopted increasingly by organizations in the global South and by those that need large numbers of identifiers. With guided exercises, by the end of the session, participants will know when and how to create and manage ARKs. We will cover:</p> <p>Why ARKs – non-paywalled, decentralized, flexible Use cases – Smithsonian, French National Library, Internet Archive Metadata for early and ongoing object development How to get started – fill out one form Minting and assigning ARK identifiers Resolvers, resolution, redirection Persistence considerations</p>
14:00 - 17:00	<p>Workshop 10 Location: SB-M415 Session Chair: Emily Bongiovanni, Carnegie Mellon University</p>
	<p>ID: 119 / W08: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs), APIs, automation, metadata</p> <p>Leverage the DataCite REST API for metadata discovery and creation Kelly Stathis, Joseph Rhoads, Bryceson Laing, Sara El-Gebali DataCite</p> <p>This workshop will cover the different functions of the DataCite REST API and how to build scripts that work with DataCite DOI metadata. Participants will gain hands-on experience with:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Information retrieval: Participants will learn how to use the DataCite REST API to search DOIs in the DataCite Metadata Store, including how to construct queries and apply filters. 2. DOI registration and metadata updates: Participants will try out DOI registration in the DataCite test system and learn how to update DOI metadata. 3. Task automation: Participants will work from Jupyter notebooks to accomplish common scenarios with the DataCite REST API—for example, harvesting metadata for a set of DOIs or executing batch changes.
14:00 - 17:00	<p>Workshop 9 Location: SB3-L111 Session Chair: Urban Andersson, Chalmers University of Technology</p>
	<p>ID: 142 / W04: 1 Workshops and Tutorials <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> DSpace, development, collaboration</p> <p>DSpace Developer Meet-Up and Q&A</p>

Tim Donohue¹, Michele Mennielli¹, Andrea Bollini², Art Lowe³

¹Lyrasis, United States; ²Science, Italy; ³Atmire, Belgium

This half day workshop provides an opportunity for developers at institutions using DSpace to discuss recent DSpace releases, share what they are working on, ask questions and find collaborators.

At the beginning of the workshop, an overview of DSpace 8.0 will be presented, with a focus on features/changes that developers may want to be aware of. Information on the upcoming roadmap to 9.0 will also be shared (based on priorities established by DSpace Steering Group). Attendees will have an opportunity to ask questions about recent releases and the upcoming roadmap.

The remainder of the workshop will provide opportunities for developer presentation and discussion. Attendees are encouraged to bring anything they have built or are planning to build for DSpace. Demonstrations are welcome/encouraged. This is an opportunity to receive feedback from other developers or find potential collaborators. DSpace Committers will be in attendance to answer questions or provide tips/tricks. Committers will similarly share any new features they may be working on (or brainstorming) for future releases.

14:00 - 17:00

Workshop 11

Location: **SB3-L112**

Session Chair: **Ellen Ramsey**, University of Virginia

ID: 153 / W07: 1

Workshops and Tutorials

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Machine learning, Automated subject indexing, Metadata

Introduction to the Annif automated indexing tool

Osma Suominen¹, Mona Lehtinen¹, Ghulam Mustafa Majaj², Juho Inkinen¹, Anna Kasprzik², Lakshmi Bashyam²

¹National Library of Finland, Finland; ²ZBW– Leibniz Information Centre for Economics

This tutorial focuses on introducing participants to Annif, a multilingual automated subject indexing tool that can enhance for example a library's metadata generation system. Better metadata contributes to easier discoverability, emphasizing Annif's – and this tutorial's – impact on information accessibility and retrieval as well. Through hands-on exercises and demos, attendees gain practical experience in setting up Annif, training algorithms with sample data, and utilizing the tool to generate subject suggestions for new documents. The tutorial covers basic and advanced usage scenarios and allows participants to deepen their understanding and proficiency in implementing Annif for efficient metadata production in library systems. We will also demonstrate the use of Annif in institutional repositories. The tutorial is aimed at anyone with an interest in library automation including developers, repository managers and metadata librarians.

Date: Tuesday, 04/June/2024

08:00 - 19:00

Registration

Opening Plenary

Location: **Drottningporten**

Session Chair: **Torsten Reimer**, University of Chicago

Session Chair: **Jessica Lindholm**, Chalmers University of Technology

09:00 - 09:40

- 09:00 - 09:05 **Introduction and housekeeping**
- 09:05 - 09:15 **Welcome to Gothenburg.** *Håkan Eriksson, First Deputy Lord Mayor of Gothenburg*
- 09:15 - 09:30 **The vision of Chalmers** *Martin Nilsson Jacobi, President, Chalmers University of Technology*
- 09:30 - 09:40 **Steering committee welcome, introductions & acknowledgements**

09:40 - 10:30

Keynote Speaker Gustav Nilsson

Location: **Drottningporten**

Gustav Nilsson is associate professor of neuroscience at Karolinska Institutet, Sweden. His work is largely in metascience: assessing and improving the transparency and reproducibility of research. Gustav is a long-standing advocate for open science and is a senior advisor to the Swedish National Data Service.

10:30 - 11:00

Coffee Break

11:00 - 12:30

24x7: Transparent and Reproducible Research

Location: **Drottningporten 1**

Session Chair: **Tomas Lunden**, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

ID: 172 / 24X701: 1

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: Open Data, Research Data Management, Data Sharing Policies, Data Access, Funding Agencies, India

Open Research Data, Data Sharing and Access Policies of the Indian Research Funding Agencies: An Overview

Pallab Pradhan¹, Lavji N Zala²

¹Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET) Centre, Gandhinagar, Gujarat, India; ²Department of Library & Information Science, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar, Gujarat, India

The paper provides a general overview of the draft, approved, and implemented open research data and data-sharing policies of the Indian research funding agencies. The Government of India, under its various ministries, departments, and autonomous agencies/bodies/councils/boards, provides funds to many academic and research organizations to fuel scientific research, advancements, and innovations across disciplines/fields in the country. The study identifies and provides an overview of the policies of the Indian research funding agencies/bodies encompassing research data management, data sharing, open data, accessibility, etc. First, extensive Google searches were made to find policy information using different keywords related to the research study. A list of Indian funding agencies that have such policies was prepared. Then, their websites were searched manually, and the required policy documents were downloaded/collected. It was found that not all funding agencies have such open data or data sharing and access policies in place. Funding departments, agencies/bodies from only 18 Government Ministries and 02 Autonomous Departments, which constitute only 33% of Ministries, have open data management, data sharing policies, and data repositories/archives in their system. The study covers policies from only selected Indian funding agencies/government bodies, i.e., DST, ICAR, ICSSR, DBT, ICMR, DGH, NIC, CSIR, ISRO, and NSE.

ID: 205 / 24X701: 2

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Open government; Open science policy–Canada; Federal Open Science Repository of Canada

The Federal Open Science Repository of Canada: A Key Destination on Canada's Roadmap to Open Science

Kathryn West, Allison Kelley

Federal Science Libraries Network, National Research Council Canada

Until now, many Government of Canada scientists and researchers have not had the infrastructure to make their scientific publications openly available. This gap has been addressed by the Federal Open Science Repository of Canada (FOSRC), a shared repository that launched January 2024 to make federally funded scientific outputs accessible to all. The FOSRC, which will help meet key recommendations of Canada's Roadmap for Open Science, is a horizontal initiative among federal departments. Collaborators include the Office of Chief Science Advisor of Canada, Shared Service Canada, the Federal Science Libraries Network/National Research Council Canada, and eight science-based departments and agencies.

The primary goal of this repository is to deliver a practical solution for a policy-driven recommendation to provide transparency and open access to Canadian research. The approach to this large-scale project was to establish a collaboration model for governance, operations, and technical development. Within this model, a business owner was established to work through governance committees for decision-making; oversee financial and operations management; liaise on product development; and ensure success for the strategic vision. Undertaking a shared repository project with varied interests is challenging and rewarding, requiring clear strategic direction, financial support, flexibility, and close collaboration.

ID: 364 / 24X701: 3

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Metadata and Discoverability
Keywords: Repositories, Data sources, Research results, Discoverability, OpenAIRE, EOSC

Making data sources discoverable in the EOSC Marketplace via OpenAIRE PROVIDE

André Vieira, Pedro Principe

University of Minho, Portugal

This lightning talk presentation aims to present the integration of services from repository managers, both from OpenAIRE and EOSC to make repositories and their contents interoperable and discoverable by a wider audience.

Institutional Repositories among other kind of data sources are key players to promote research transparency, by offering services to publish research results in open access, contributing to the fulfilment of the open science principles, specifically to make scholarly research accessible to everyone, and to increase its impact on society. On this context, OpenAIRE and EOSC-Future project are offering integrated services and interoperability guidelines to increase the interoperability and visibility of data sources and research results.

The integration between OpenAIRE PROVIDE and EOSC Service Provider Dashboard contributes to simplify processes, where on the one hand OpenAIRE allows the registration and content aggregation and, on the other, EOSC allows it to be displayed on its marketplace, contributing to improve the discoverability of repositories and their content, without duplicating efforts by the repository manager.

This lightning talk will outline the main procedures to onboard data sources in EOSC, clarifying the integration between OpenAIRE services and EOSC, aiming to clarify data source managers about its use and main benefits.

ID: 372 / 24X701: 4

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Research Transparency and Openness, Manara Research Data Repository, FAIR Data Management

Enhancing Research Transparency and Openness in Qatar: The Role of Manara Research Repository

Marcin Werla, dr Arif Shaon, dr Alwaleed Alkhaja

Qatar National Library, Qatar

Qatar has witnessed substantial growth in its research landscape, marking a strategic shift towards a knowledge-driven economy. This evolution, crucial for sustaining national development and improving living standards, is supported by key entities like the Qatar National Research Fund (QNRF). However, challenges persist in ensuring transparency due to decentralized research data management practices across institutions. This presentation addresses these challenges, emphasizing the importance of a nationally coordinated approach. It highlights the role of Qatar National Library's (QNL) Manara Data Repository in promoting transparency, curation, and Open Access to Qatari research output. Manara's operational model features a comprehensive metadata schema, promoting discoverability and potential reuse. The repository advocates for Open Access licenses and encourages FAIR data management practices, fostering collaboration and transparency in Qatar's research community. Join us to explore Manara's impact on enhancing research transparency and openness, contributing to Qatar's journey towards a knowledge-based economy aligned with national objectives.

ID: 374 / 24X701: 5

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Research integrity, Publication Practices, Open Archive Management, Metadata Quality

Beyond access, Upholding the Integrity of Scientific Publications in HAL Open Archive

Nathalie Fargier

CNRS, France

Research integrity, vital for scientific credibility and public trust, extends to the quality, reliability, and credibility of scientific literature. Open repositories play a pivotal role in upholding scientific publication integrity by facilitating the deposit, preservation, and dissemination of diverse publications and ensuring open and high-quality metadata.

HAL, the French national open archive, underscores institutional affiliation, publication version, and peer review status. HAL has established dedicated procedures to organize and address reports of research integrity breaches concerning HAL publications, involving the user community in the process. The initiative led to the publication of detailed statements of policies and submission requirements. Additionally, it facilitated updates to the archive's terms of use with a clear definition of mutual responsibilities, the design of a process diagram, and the establishment of an authority composed of research integrity officers from academic institutions to support HAL managers.

The presentation will cover the legal, ethical and organisational issues addressed, outlining upcoming measures to ensure metadata provenance, traceability, conflict management, and synchronization.

ID: 392 / 24X701: 6

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Publications Repositories, Data Repositories, Open Science Impacts, Open Science Indicators

Open Science Indicators: PATHOS project handbook and repositories use cases

Pedro Principe, Antónia Correia

University of Minho, Portugal

Open Access to publications and data, made possible by Repositories, holds the promise of increasing visibility of research (as it has the potential for more people to discover and download research outputs); transparency of research, allowing for verifications and reproducibility; interdisciplinary research and increase in collaborations; citations; and societal benefits such as a more democratic and equitable world. But is it so? Some studies have already dealt with one or more of these topics, but a more holistic approach seems to be lacking.

PathOS is a Horizon Europe project aiming to collect evidence of Open Science effects, by studying the impact pathways (context, resources, activities, outputs, outcomes and impacts), doing an extensive literature review, studying the causal effects, producing a Handbook of Open Science Indicators and applying selected indicators into six case studies, four of them based on publication repositories, data repositories and open infrastructures. This talk details how the indicators were selected and are being operationalized by the latter, making the case for their use and the investment in these open infrastructures.

11:00 - 12:30

Developer Track Session 1

Location: **Drottningporten 2**

Session Chair: **Jonas Gilbert**, University of Borås

ID: 174 / DV01: 1

Developer Track

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Repository metadata, Scientometric analyses, Data preparation, Unstructured and structured data

Repositories as data sources – good practice when preparing data for scientometric studies

Alysson Fernandes Mazoni

Unicamp, Brazil

As more and more repositories are available, the metadata available there are increasingly used for scientometric analyses, including for evaluative purposes. Local repositories are often an important complementary source as they gather output not commonly available in the large databases currently in use. As these local repositories commonly struggle to keep up with new technical demands, for example for interoperability, data equity is a problem to be solved. This is also the case when repository metadata have to be adapted to fit for scientometric analyses. To gather and extract metadata for such analyses may be cumbersome due to variations in structures and formats. This proposal summarizes recent work with several repositories from around the world such as SciELO and African Journals Online. Current examples of how to process and structure in order to be able to combine data from different sources will be shared, as well as best practice examples gained from this experience. These repositories commonly gather material from underrepresented communities, for example non-English material. Pooling the experiences of gathering data from these different repositories may help leverage the work done locally, and make the data widely available for analyses.

	<p>ID: 207 / DV01: 2 Developer Track <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Metadata-Driven Content Control, Cora Platform Development for DiVA, Open source</p> <p>Cora: Empowering DiVA's Next Major Version with Metadata-Driven Flexibility Olov McKie, Pere Bartroli Simó Uppsala University Library, Sweden</p> <p>This proposal introduces Cora, an open source platform developed by Uppsala University Library, designed to handle structured metadata and associated binary files. Cora brings a unique approach to content control by letting metadata guide the content stored in the repository.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 219 / DV01: 3 Developer Track <i>Topics:</i> Responsible Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI), Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> ANN Search, OSS Repository System, AI/ML, Processing Pipelines</p> <p>Hybrid ML/AI driven search as cataloging aid in Archipelago Commons Diego Alberto Pino Metropolitan New York Library Council, United States of America</p> <p>In this presentation we will explain and showcase how Semantic and Image Similarity Search is being developed and implemented in Archipelago Commons, an OSS repository system. This new feature will be publicly available and deployed by default for all our users starting on version 1.5.0. This functionality brings a hybrid approach on AI/ML driven search and application to our OSS repository system. By adding new Services to our existing Docker stack, using NLP and LoD entities for important validation context, and providing end user facing tools we ensure our community has complete control of what is included/excluded and how results to queries are exposed to the world. Our hybrid approach also entails integrating an embeddings/features extraction pipeline, vector based search on our current Solr indexes, Spotify's Annoy as a Service, and a custom IIF Content Search API 2.x implementation with Binary search capability.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 228 / DV01: 4 Developer Track <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> dspace, entities, upgrade, migration, linked data</p> <p>Authority to Entities: A DSpace 7 migration case study Kim Shepherd, Pascal-Nicolas Becker The Library Code GmbH, Germany</p> <p>DSpace 7 introduced the concept of entities and relationships which provide a way for the repository to represent many concepts in open access publishing.</p> <p>One of the most obvious use cases of this new framework is a way of representing the relationships between people (authors, editors, project managers) and works like publications and projects. If you are migrating from a previous version of DSpace, you might already have authority control in place.</p> <p>In 2023, The Library Code GmbH completed a large migration of a DSpace 6 institutional research repository to DSpace 7. A large part of this work involved the conversion of nearly 40,000 authority-controlled metadata values to entities and relationships, where institutional authors would now be represented by a Person entity with relationships to Publication and Project entities.</p> <p>This presentation will have a technical view on entities, relationships and data migration. We will share our experience using entities and relationships in DSpace 7. We will discuss the technical approach taken, its benefits and challenges and share the lessons learned during this project. We hope to help demystify one of DSpace's largest new features by presenting how we achieved this large migration.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 294 / DV01: 5 Developer Track <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems <i>Keywords:</i> cost data, cost transparency, OAI-PMH, xml schema, sustainable publishing</p> <p>Repositories as a Corner Stone of Publication Cost Transparency : XML, OAI-PMH and all that Lisa-Marie Stein¹, Alexander Wagner¹, Julia Bartlewski², Christoph Broschinski², Gernot Deinzer³, Dirk Pieper², Bianca Schweighofer³, Colin Sipp³, Silke Weisheit³ ¹Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY, Germany; ²University of Bielefeld, Germany; ³University of Regensburg, Germany</p> <p>With the rise of Gold Open Access publishing in "author pays" models a new kind of metadata gains importance: costs directly associated with publications. Adding so-called transformative agreements as well as scholarly led Open Access to the mix further increases their importance, as cost transparency has to be a guiding principle for sustainability.</p> <p>Repositories provide high quality metadata in various formats via established interfaces. Enhancing these metadata by cost data thus makes them a potential corner stone to achieve the desired transparency.</p> <p>Therefore, the project openCost developed, together with the community, a XML schema to model cost data both for individual articles and, most recently, to handle contracts.</p> <p>We give an in-depth view of the openCost schema, demonstrate real world implementations and provide some glimpses on an associated workflow to collect the data. This will enable developers to gain an understanding of the requirements for adding openCost compatibility to existing repository systems.</p> <p>The openCost partner University of Bielefeld already implemented harvesting of the openCost format via OAI-PMH for their own, openly available aggregator platform OpenAPC. Their openly available metadata store allows a wide variety of analyses and thus showcases the strength of the openCost approach.</p>
<p>11:00 - 12:30</p>	<p>Presentations: Regional Collaborations Location: Drottningporten 3 Session Chair: Kathryn Cassidy, Trinity College Dublin</p>
	<p>ID: 130 / PR01: 1 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Repository, Open, Alignment, Community, Collaboration</p> <p>Building Community to Coordinate Ireland's Fragmented Open Repository Network Cillian Joy¹, Stephanie Ronan², Christopher Loughnane¹ ¹University of Galway, Ireland; ²Marine Institute</p> <p>This talk details a transformative two-year initiative led by the University of Galway, a key player of the National Open Research Forum (NORF) National Open Research Action Plan. Focused on aligning Ireland's open repositories with international best practices, the project adopts a sustainable, community-centric approach. With the aim of transitioning from a fragmented to a cohesive repository approach, the project emphasises collaboration and integration, both nationally and internationally. Findings underscore the critical need for metadata alignment to support ambitious open research goals. The survey reveals a fragmented landscape, necessitating comprehensive national cooperation and coordination. Challenges include disparities in staffing, resource allocation, and reliance on external hosting providers, highlighting the urgent need for dedicated personnel and robust resource management. The talk outlines recommendations, advocating for collaborative initiatives, training, metadata standardisation, and national alignment. It highlights the importance of shared infrastructure, technical support, and advocacy to address challenges and enhance open repository networks in Ireland. As the project progresses into its next phase, it stands as a compelling case study for networks aspiring to strengthen their open repository landscape guided by international best practices. We show a data-driven exploration of Ireland's journey, contributing significantly to the global advancement of open repositories.</p>

ID: 232 / PR01: 2

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability
Keywords: cross-border partnerships, historical archives, internationalization, digitization

Collaboration Across Borders

Jessica Barlow¹, Lisa Lamont¹, Matt Ferrill¹, Hilario Castillo Castillo², Kristofer Patrón Soberano¹

¹San Diego State University, United States of America; ²Archivo Histórico de Tijuana

This presentation will describe a digitization partnership between the San Diego State University (SDSU) Library, the SDSU Center for Regional Sustainability, and the Archivo Histórico de Tijuana, housed within the Instituto Municipal de Arte y Cultura (IMAC). The collaboration addresses IMAC's desire to make their diverse and unique holdings more accessible online to the public and SDSU's desire to increase access to these unique holdings while respecting the needs and autonomy of the Archivo. Their unique and important holdings include photographs and papers documenting history and evolution of the US-Mexico border region. This presentation will also address the challenges and opportunities associated with an international collaboration, including the administrative issues such as contracting and paying for work in another country, the human issues of working respectfully in the archives of a foreign city, securing funding for international projects, creating and displaying metadata in multiple languages, and developing our digital repository based on the open source software Archipelago. The presentation will include the perspectives of both the Tijuana team and the SDSU team and outline our plans and hopes for sustaining the partnership and encouraging community engagement. The presentation will showcase the online Tijuana collections and invite feedback.

ID: 354 / PR01: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: repository, research data management, long-term preservation, open source, community

PHAIDRA's Journey Towards Sustainable and Open Repositories

Raman Ganguly

University of Vienna, Austria

While universities provide diverse data management options, researchers often face post-project challenges in maintaining, accessing, and securing data within non-customized infrastructures.

PHAIDRA, an open-source platform originating from the University of Vienna addresses long-term preservation needs across disciplines. PHAIDRA's key strength lies in bridging the cultural gap among researchers, IT departments, and librarians, who often have different perspectives on long-term availability of data. Thus fostering a sustainable ecosystem.

The presentation will showcase PHAIDRA's user-centric design, use of discipline-spanning standards, and API integration for enhanced accessibility. As a testament to open-source principles, PHAIDRA actively engages its community, ensuring continuous improvement aligned with the FAIR Data principles.

Exploring PHAIDRA's alignment with UN SDGs, particularly SDG 9 and 17, the presentation will highlight its commitment to industry, innovation, and infrastructure, showcasing how the platform exemplifies advancements in data fairness, open research, and responsible technology use. The presentation will furthermore reflect on the project's 15-year journey, emphasizing collective efforts for the enduring impact of open-source initiatives in the dynamic field of research data management.

11:00 - 12:30

Presentations: Repositories Implementations

Location: **Brevsorterarsalen 1**

Session Chair: **Ellen Ramsey**, University of Virginia

ID: 106 / PR02: 1

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: sustainability, data models, system migrations, next-generation repositories

How to Rebuild a Jumbo Jet at 30,000 Feet: Strategies for Digital Repository Migration

Michael Giarlo, Aaron Collier

Stanford University, United States of America

In support of research, teaching and learning, the Stanford Digital Repository (SDR) is a network of systems and services that house the digital collections of Stanford University Libraries (SUL). Collections in SDR include Google-scanned books, student dissertations and theses, University Archives, Allen Ginsberg's papers, Parker Library, and the Fugitive U.S. Agencies Web Archive, to name a handful. As of late 2022, SDR holds over 5 million digital objects composed of more than 530 million content files. SDR is extremely heterogeneous along several facets, including content types (e.g., books, images, web archives, GIS datasets) and file types.

For the past 4 years, SUL has been working towards migrating SDR to a new datastore and data model. We successfully completed the migration this year. In this presentation, we will describe the motivations for this work and the strategies used to accomplish the migration. These strategies may be repurposeable in other production system migrations: adopting a validatable data model, abstracting the datastore behind an API, separating concerns, testing metadata mappings against production, writing reports to understand complex data, templating unit tests, performing a rolling migration, and incorporating migration into ongoing project work.

ID: 196 / PR02: 2

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Harvesting, national collaboration, open science, OpenAIRE

Switching the national portal of The Netherlands to OpenAire within six months

Rutger De Jong¹, Chris Baars², Alessia Bardi³, Maurice Vanderfeesten⁴

¹Leiden University, Netherlands, The; ²DANS, Netherlands, The; ³CNR-ISTI / OpenAIRE; ⁴Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Netherlands, The

In January 2023 the national harvester for The Netherlands (Narcis) announced to stop their services within a few months, leaving The Netherlands without a central portal for their scholarly output. Even though the content of the larger repositories may be well indexed in scholarly search engines, the national portal was important for the visibility of Dutch research output for several reasons. First, the content was not limited to major universities; smaller research organizations and universities were connected and delivered unique materials (e.g. research reports). Second, the audience of Narcis is not just academics: due to its focus on national output and added value such as the experts guide, it was a source of knowledge for journalists, companies and policy makers that are less likely to use scholarly search engines. Third, the content was not limited to publications, but also covered datasets, software and funding information and connected these items through a PID-graph. A taskforce was created to quickly prevent the loss of visibility of the national output. By setting clear goals, monitoring and having a good collaboration with OpenAIRE, a new research portal based on OpenAIRE CONNECT and a Monitor dashboard were set up before July: the Netherlands Research Portal.

ID: 162 / PR02: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Stakeholder Engagement, Human-Centered Design, Transparency

Transparency and Transformation: Reimagining Harvard's Digital Repository Service

Stefano Cossu, Miriam Leigh, Vitaly Zakuta

Harvard University, United States of America

This presentation will describe the Harvard Library DRS Futures Project. It will then detail the initial exploratory phase and principles that informed the requirements and design philosophies that underpin the development phase. Finally, it will share lessons learned and upcoming challenges as the project enters its third year.

11:00 - 12:30

Panel: How to Make Repository Content Indexed and Discoverable

Location: **Brevsorterarsalen 2**

Session Chair: **Leigh Stork**, University of Strathclyde

	<p>ID: 279 / PAN01: 1 Panels <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Discoverability, indexing, scholarly search, harvesting, interoperability, aggregation, machine access</p> <p>How to make repository content indexed and discoverable Petr Knoth¹, Martin Klein², George Macgregor³, Matteo Cancellieri¹, Paul Walk⁴</p> <p>¹CORE, The Open University, United Kingdom; ²Los Alamos National Laboratory; ³University of Glasgow; ⁴Antleaf Ltd.</p> <p>Millions of users access scholarly indexes each month. A solitary repository, if not correctly indexed, will languish alone. According to the Confederation of Open Access Repositories (Rodriguez, 2011), each individual repository is of limited value for research: the real power of Open Access lies in the possibility of connecting and tying together repositories. However, even today, many repositories are not yet configured in a way that would enable their resources to be comprehensively indexed in scholarly infrastructures.</p> <p>Ensuring the discoverability of repository research outputs is crucial for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maximizing the impact and reach of scholarly works - Making research visible to the general public - Facilitating research collaborations - Delivering on the open science mission - Enabling systematic literature reviews - Monitoring compliance with funding agency policies - Promoting reproducibility - Fostering innovation <p>We propose a panel session that will provide a set of practical wide-ranging recommendations for repositories to enable, validate and monitor the indexing of their repository content. By implementing the wide-ranging recommendations and principles discussed in this panel session, repositories will be able to markedly improve their content's discoverability.</p>
<p>11:00 - 12:30</p>	<p>Presentations: Institutional Repositories Location: Brevsorterarsalen 3 Session Chair: William J. Nixon, Research Libraries UK (RLUK)</p>
	<p>ID: 404 / PR21: 1 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation <i>Keywords:</i> Repository, Research data management, System integration</p> <p>System integration for efficient publication of research results through collaboration between researchers and librarians Masaharu Hayashi, Yusuke Komiyama, Jun-ichi Onami, Kazutsuna Yamaji National Institute of Informatics, Japan</p> <p>Research institutions, traditionally using institutional repositories to disseminate research outputs from affiliated researchers, are increasingly recognizing their value as platforms for publishing foundational research outputs, including papers, data, and methods, in line with the growing trend towards open science, thereby ensuring transparency and fairness and promoting the reuse of these outputs. In this background, we are developing the NII Research Data Cloud (NII RDC), an information infrastructure that supports open science and research fairness and promotes data-driven research. We aim to develop a method that streamlines the entire process, from generating research outputs to publishing research outputs, thereby reducing the burden on researchers. We will integrate three platforms that are key components of NII RDC to streamline the entire process. As a result of integrating the three platforms, we have confirmed that publishing and searching for research outputs produced by researchers is possible. We have outlined a policy for dividing roles between researchers and librarians in creating metadata for publishing research outputs. In the future, we aim to refine the metadata creation process further. This refinement will help reduce the research workload and advance us towards a world where research outputs can be published more rapidly.</p>
	<p>ID: 229 / PR21: 2 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Usage, statistics, open, assessment, repository strategy</p> <p>Open COUNTER-conformant Institutional Repository Usage Statistics (IRUS):Thinking Beyond Top 10 Lists Sheila Rabun¹, Paige Morgan²</p> <p>¹Lyrisis, United States of America; ²University of Delaware, United States of America</p> <p>This session focuses on how Jisc's Institutional Repository Usage Statistics (IRUS) service has helped US institutions like Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), University of Michigan, and University of Delaware to align and assess usage metrics across library resources, benchmark usage against peer repositories at other institutions, and invest in open infrastructure to advocate more effectively about the value of making scholarly research material openly available. We use statistics as a concrete starting point for a larger discussion of strategies for articulating the value of repositories to different stakeholders (including researchers and administrators); and look at IRUS in the context of other complementary initiatives, such as the Open Global Data Citation Corpus. By considering these different projects, we hope to make space for a wide-ranging discussion of approaches to repository assessment and consider more broadly what generalized repository statistics can and can't accomplish.</p>
	<p>ID: 256 / PR21: 3 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Comparative study, InvenioRDM, DSpace, Hyrax</p> <p>Comparing some basic features of three institutional software repository platforms Anusha Ranganathan, Steven Eardley, Hrafn Malmquist Cottage Labs, United Kingdom</p> <p>This presentation showcases the default functionality offered by three popular open source IR software platforms: DSpace, Hyrax and InvenioRDM when ingesting and publishing typical content. Although each platform is configurable, they come with default metadata schemas and design decisions that drive the ability to personalize the application. Various aspects of these basic use cases will be discussed, as well as the effort needed to implement light thematic branding. Support for more advanced features such as PIDs, single sign-on, full-text indexing, faceted search and browsing, support for publishing workflows, integrations with external services to enhance the functionality and interoperability will be very briefly touched upon for the sake of brevity.</p>
<p>12:30 - 13:30</p>	<p>Lunch Break</p>
<p>13:30 - 15:00</p>	<p>Presentations: Open and Sustainable Infrastructure Location: Drottningporten 1 Session Chair: Camilla Lindelow, University of Borås</p>
	<p>ID: 143 / PR03: 1 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Community-developed software, APIs, open science, open scholarship, software infrastructure</p> <p>New Frontiers in Community-Led API Development: A Case Study on the OSF Gretchen Mary Gueguen, Nadja Oertelt Center for Open Science, United States of America</p> <p>This presentation will review the new Open Scholarship Open Source Environment API developed by the Center for Open Science as part of the Open Science Framework (OSF) platform and will discuss future development plans. It will also discuss the process for developing the requirements for the API with community members in order to support multiple functionalities. We will close by</p>

highlighting lessons learned from developing community-supported infrastructure for open scholarship. We believe the discussion will be a contribution to ongoing discussions of not only the actual infrastructure available for doing all types of scholarly research, but also the challenges and opportunities presented by community-developed software that integrates with and supports digital repositories.

ID: 304 / PR03: 2

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: open infrastructure, discovery, data repositories, content repositories, platforms

Infra Finder: Increasing visibility of repositories as open infrastructure

Lauren B. Collister

Invest in Open Infrastructure, United States of America

Infra Finder is a new tool developed by Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI, investinopen.org) for advocates, decision-makers, and creators in the open infrastructure space. It is open-source and free to use. In its first release in January 2024, Infra Finder contains a standard set of information about 56 open infrastructure tools and services enabling the sharing of research data and publications that audiences can use to identify services, increase adoption, and foster development and investment in open infrastructure.

In this session, we will provide an overview of the development of Infra Finder, including both our survey of related tools and services in this space and the results from our interviews and focus groups that helped refine the information presented in the tool. We will demonstrate Infra Finder and the content and data repositories currently included in the tool, and detail how interested representatives of repository and other open infrastructure services can nominate their projects for inclusion.

ID: 145 / PR03: 3

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems

Keywords: Sustainability, cloud solutions, cost management, Amazon Web Services

Lowering the Barrier to Entry for Digital Repository Management by Leveraging Cloud-Native Solutions

Favencio Calvo, Bryan Brown

Florida State University, United States of America

In the rapidly evolving landscape of digital repositories, the challenge of managing costs and technical complexity often poses a significant barrier to entry, especially for smaller institutions and those in developing regions. This presentation explores an innovative approach to surmounting these challenges by leveraging cloud-native solutions, with a specific focus on Amazon Web Services (AWS). Our organization's journey in transitioning to a cloud-based infrastructure illustrates how cloud-native technologies can streamline repository management, enhance scalability, and significantly reduce operational costs.

Through a detailed case study, we will demonstrate the practical application of AWS services in optimizing data storage, ensuring high availability, and facilitating global access to digital content. Our experience sheds light on the nuances of integrating AWS into existing digital repository frameworks, highlighting both the successes and the challenges encountered.

Key discussion points will include the strategic selection of AWS services to meet specific repository needs, the cost-benefit analysis of cloud migration, and the long-term implications for repository sustainability. We will also delve into how our model promotes inclusivity by making digital repository infrastructure more accessible to a broader range of institutions.

ID: 225 / PR03: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Sustainable Repositories; Oxford Common File Layout, R0-Crate

From "R-Drive to RRKive" – a comprehensive, open and sustainable set of principles and tools for low (and high) resource archival-repositories

Peter Sefton¹, Robert McClellan¹, Michael Lynch², Moises Sacal Bonequi¹, Nick Thieberger³

¹University of Queensland; ²University of Sydney; ³University of Melbourne

We present a toolkit for sustainable archival repositories, with metadata and storage standards as well as APIs and data portals that can be assembled by communities with various levels of resourcing into repository solutions at a variety of scales, with fallback to offline operation. Tools are designed to work in low-resource environments allowing communities to have agency and control over their materials. We prioritize sustainability, simplicity, standardization, linked-data description and clear licensing over user interface features, in line with Suleman's keynote presentation at OR2023, while still being able to drive rich, full-featured services when resources allow and fall back to a sustainable core if needed.

Much of the data we work with is subject to Indigenous Cultural Intellectual property (ICIP) rights, controlled by First Nations peoples guided by Indigenous data sovereignty principles; we must ensure it is handled in a conscientious and culturally responsible manner.

Making data Accessible does not always mean Open Access – under both research ethics and the CARE and FAIR principles, data by and about humans needs access control and licensing. Our framework deals with these issues and is built from the ground up to be "as open as possible, as closed as needed".

13:30 - 15:00

Presentations: Working Towards Inclusive Metadata

Location: **Drottningporten 2**

Session Chair: **Ellen Ramsey**, University of Virginia

ID: 182 / PR04: 1

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: metadata, inclusive language, description, conscious editing

Community and User-Centered Description: Inclusive and conscious metadata as a means of expanding access

Keila Zayas Ruiz, Rhea Ray

Florida State University, United States of America

Florida State University and the Sunshine State Digital Network have been working to implement inclusive description practices in our online repositories and discovery layers. Through inclusive description centered on an active, critical awareness of bias, privilege, and power and an ethos of deliberate care used in the assessment, creation, and refinement of descriptive texts we are increasing accessibility of our collections in unserved and underserved communities seeking meaningful connections with their histories. Learn about our approach and how these practices can be implemented to expand access and increase discovery of content in our open repositories.

ID: 114 / PR04: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Metadata modelling, repository resource discovery, scholarly graph, repository harvesting and aggregation, persistent identifiers

Exploring the concept of 'custodianship' in harvesting repository resources and graphing their relations: Rioxx version 3.0

George Macgregor¹, Petr Knoth², Paul Walk³, Nicola Dowson⁴, Michael Eadie¹, Beverley Jones⁵, Agustina Martínez-García⁶

¹University of Glasgow, United Kingdom; ²CORE & The Open University, United Kingdom; ³Antleaf Ltd, United Kingdom; ⁴The Open University, United Kingdom; ⁵University of Sheffield, United Kingdom; ⁶University of Cambridge, United Kingdom

This submission addresses concepts associated with Rioxx version 3.0, the schema and specification for which was published in late 2023, following feedback gleaned during OR2023. 'Rioxx: The Research Output Schema' proposes a metadata profile to better ensure superior harvesting and ergo aggregation of scholarly content. It also promote greater semantic interoperability, as well as the graphing of essential research output relations. To assist with its metadata modelling, Rioxx version 3.0 introduces the concept of direct and external custodianship. This submission will explore this concept, establish how custodianship is reflected in the Rioxx schema, and

demonstrate how such modelling benefits both repositories and external software agents (such as harvesters and aggregators). The submission will also demonstrate how Rioxx can be used to underpin aspects of open research policy monitoring.

ID: 258 / PR04: 3

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: open knowledge, digitization, decolonization

Decolonizing Metadata for Open Access

Amanda Figueroa

Curationist

Museums, archives, galleries, and libraries have balanced their responsibility to protect the world's most important cultural artifacts with their roles as important pillars of public education. However, these goals become increasingly at odds with each other if the institution doesn't take a deliberately decolonial, and anticolonial, stance on the metadata that accompanies the object even to open access destinations like Wiki Commons, Internet Archive, and Curationist. Left unexamined, these records still carry the legacies of colonization, visible in the metadata of digitized collections from major institutions like the British Museum.

This presentation outlines the necessary role of decolonial practice in GLAM-field digitization projects as well as in the digital tools that make this content available to public audiences. By centering on the co-developed metadata tools of Curationist, we will offer not only an introduction to this platform and its uses to digital art and open education, but also a method of online community development that centers indigenous data sovereignty, community engagement, and decolonization practices to rebalance the power dynamic in collections-based open education.

ID: 128 / PR04: 4

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Metadata quality, data quality assessment, bibliometrics

What do open global scholarly metadata datasets contain? Investigating the metadata quality of data associated to underrepresented communities in big aggregators of open repositories

Simon Willemin

ETH Library, ETH Zurich, Switzerland

In comparison to established commercial bibliometric datasets, open datasets such as OpenAlex and OpenAIRE have not only the advantage of allowing greater transparency. They also have less restrictive selection processes, which allows for a better representation of underrepresented communities. However, since the open repositories used as sources follow various standards, providers of big datasets need to go through metadata aggregation and metadata enrichment processes. Such processes are not always carefully documented, and it is therefore difficult to understand which kind of data they include, and which metadata quality is to be expected.

This presentation handles two questions: How can we understand which methods big aggregators use to aggregate and to enrich the metadata they retrieve? Which practices enable some communities to outperform, in terms of metadata quality, other comparable communities in big aggregators? To answer, I will present results from the project TOBI, in which tools to understand the structure of datasets and to evaluate metadata quality are designed. Those tools and the information they provide are not only relevant for organizations who want to use transparent and sustainable data, but also for open repository managers who want to ensure visibility and dissemination of data of the highest quality.

13:30 - 15:00

Presentations: Utilizing DSpace

Location: **Drottningporten 3**

Session Chair: **Ianthe Sutherland**, University of Edinburgh

ID: 183 / PR05: 1

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Open Science, DSpace, Ibict, Digital Repository.

DSpace Updater Tool as a support tool for the Brazilian Digital Repository Network

Tatyane Guedes Martins da Silva, Marcio Ribeiro Gurgel do Amaral, Cássio Teixeira de Moraes, Marcel Garcia de Souza, Washington Luís Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo

Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (Ibict), Brazil

Scientific publications repositories contribute to the access, use and reuse of information, which benefits the advent of Open Science in Brazil through the Brazilian Network of Digital Repositories (RBRD). This proposal aims to present and make available to the world the DSpace Updater Tool and its contribution to the development of RBRD, both created by the Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (Ibict). Ibict is the Brazilian governmental body, which operates at the forefront of Open Science, promoting and participating in the introduction of national and international good practices, using collaborative work to promote Open Science in various services and products, highlighting in this article the creation of digital repositories in Brazilian institutions. Documentary and descriptive research was used as a methodological strategy. As a result, we found that using the tool makes it possible to install or update DSpace software quickly and pragmatically.

ID: 255 / PR05: 2

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: DSpace, version, security, distribution, legacy systems

The Distribution of DSpace

Hrafn Malmquist

Cottage Labs, United Kingdom

This talk presents the results of original research into the distribution and geolocation of installations of the institutional repository software platform DSpace. Its novelty lies in its approach in aggregating existing sources on DSpace installations, performing deduplication and by probing and scraping the installations to gain further information. Comparison between two different points in time with over a year between them will be presented to give an idea of the pace of upgrades. The major differences between versions will be explained with a focus on the security vulnerabilities of end of life versions (versions prior to 7). The talk will elaborate shortly on what the author thinks this means for the future of support, maintenance and upgrades in the community.

ID: 261 / PR05: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: DSpace, entities, relationship, migration

DSpace's entities in practice

Pascal-Nicolas Becker, Kim Shepherd

The Library Code GmbH, Germany

With DSpace 7, configurable entities were introduced. Entities were one of the major new features introduced in DSpace 7, along with the new user interface and architecture. In 2023, The Library Code completed a major migration of an institutional research repository from DSpace 6 to DSpace 7. In DSpace 6, the repository made heavy use of DSpace's authority control. It collects information about publications, student works, and research projects. We migrated the information using DSpace 7 entities and relationships, adopted and modified the DSpace 7 submission process, and integrated an external data source for information about institutional staff and students.

In this presentation, we will show what DSpace's entities can provide, how they can be used in practice, what this means for the submission process, and how you can take advantage of entities and relationships to present your information. We will discuss the approaches we took, our reasoning behind key decisions, challenges we faced during the migration, and lessons learned.

The discussion won't be highly technical, focusing on the functionality of a modern DSpace 7-based repository using entities, relationships, and the angular submission interface. The technical details will be covered in a presentation in the Developer Track of

OR24.

ID: 320 / PR05: 4

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Repository upgrades, DSpace 7, system resources, shared infrastructure, Amazon Web Services, community collaboration

“There’s no cow on the ice”: How we learned to stop worrying and love DSpace 7

Kristi L. Park, Nicholas Woodward

Texas Digital Library, United States of America

In 2023, the Texas Digital Library upgraded its 24 DSpace repositories to DSpace 7.6. These upgrades of production repositories -- taking place between June and November 2023 -- were the culmination of many preceding months of planning, testing, documentation, and training in collaboration with TDL’s member institutions. This presentation will provide an overview of this upgrade journey, starting from a state of worry and concern over the readiness of both DSpace 7 itself and of our community to embrace this brand new user experience. Through extensive preparation and full engagement of our members in the planning and execution of the upgrades, we learned together that there was no need to worry -- or, using the Swedish expression, “There is no cow on the ice.”

13:30 - 15:00

Presentations: Global and Cultural Heritage Collections

Location: **Brevsorterarsalen 1**

Session Chair: **Cecilia Granell**, Chalmers University of Technology

ID: 328 / PR06: 1

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Responsible Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI), Repository Systems

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; doctoral research repositories; global communities

Exploring ‘the global community’ in open doctoral research repositories: contradictions and conflicts in the research community of the EThOS repository.

Catherine Montgomery¹, Jenny Basford²

¹Durham University, United Kingdom; ²British Library, London, United Kingdom

EThOS is digital repository containing a near-complete aggregation of all doctoral theses ever awarded by UK Higher Education institutions, consisting of over 600,000 records from over 140 institutions. The EThOS collection offers a significant opportunity to diversify the forms and sources of knowledge production in a digital era. This presentation focuses on a project building impact from the knowledge and research of UK doctoral theses, making them accessible for research and community organisations, developing a prototype of a Search Tool which has performs clustering and text summarisation. The summarisation algorithm crawls through each thesis identifying important phrases and stitching them together to form new sentences that are quickly readable.

Using researched examples from the EThOS collection we explore the ways in which the new Artificial Intelligence tool can enable the creation of a virtual global community, although there are contradictions inherent in this. EThOS presents opportunities to surface themes and construct knowledge on an almost infinite range of topics, drawing on the theses which date back to 1650 and cover all disciplines. The examples highlighted construct the nature of the virtual and real community engendered through EThOS and raises issues of participation, ownership and exclusions in open research repositories.

ID: 367 / PR06: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Data integration, Heritage science data in context, Institution-wide search, Complexities

Sharing heritage in context: The difficult journey to a unified data platform

Stephanie Buyle, Edwin De Roock, Wim Fremout, Véronique Van der Stede, Erik Buelinckx, Emmanuel Di Pretoro

Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA), Belgium

The Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage (KIK-IRPA) is enhancing heritage science data management and dissemination through its innovative BALaT+ platform. This initiative aims to unify diverse data sources into a single, FAIR digital platform, offering an in-depth context for each heritage object. BALaT+ tackles the integration of varied, heterogeneous datasets, typically found in KIK-IRPA’s ‘intervention files’, which are managed across different systems. Elasticsearch is used as the indexer responsible for managing the aggregated data and making it searchable. The development of BALaT+ involved addressing the complexities of presenting a holistic context for research conducted on heritage objects, leading to a tailored in-house development approach. This process was marked by continuous adaptation to technological advancements and reassessment of methodologies to manage and present heritage data effectively. Different repositories seemed possible candidates until we finally settled on one that satisfied our requirements. This proposal aims to document KIK-IRPA’s journey towards developing BALaT+ and the valuable lessons we’ve learned along the way.

ID: 376 / PR06: 3

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Digital Cultural Heritage, DSpace, Digital Libraries, Data Model, IIIF

Rethinking Digital Libraries Paradigms: moving Digital Cultural Heritage Collections to DSpace 7/8

Andrea Bollini, Claudio Cortese, Andrea Barbasso, Irene Buso, Riccardo Fazio, Damiano Fiorenza, Giuseppe Digilio, Benedetta Gandolini, Emilia Groppo, Stefano Maffei, Vincenzo Mecca, Susanna Mornati, Luigi Andrea Pascarelli, Immacolata Scancarello, Francesco Pio Scognamiglio, Federico Verlicchi

4Science, Italy

The release of DSpace 7 with all the new technologies and features it implements, represents a momentous change, opening up the application to new and broader perspectives. In particular, it makes the product much more attractive to the cultural heritage domain. As a result, several organizations are starting to implement or migrating Digital Libraries to DSpace 7 or to the most recent version 8. Based on 4Science’s experience in managing more than twenty DSpace-based Cultural Heritage projects, this contribution aims to present the challenges of starting a Digital Library based on DSpace, both from scratch or migrating data. The presentation will also illustrate how creating a DSpace-based Digital Library can take such applications to the next level, allowing to explore and analyze documents in relation to other documents and to all the information helping to define their context, or rather their different contexts (historical, geographical, cultural, etc.) and providing tools to communicate digital cultural heritage in different ways for different audiences.

ID: 226 / PR06: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Digital Scholarship, Static Site Generator, IIIF Collections, Reusability

Canopy IIIF: Remix Digital Assets From Cultural Heritage Repositories

Adam Joseph Arling, Matthew Randolph Jordan

Northwestern University, United States of America

Canopy IIIF is an open-source static-site generator designed for fast creation, contextualization, and customization of discovery-focused digital scholarship and collections websites using IIIF APIs. Leveraging a single IIIF Presentation Collection as its transparent data source, Canopy generates a browsable, searchable, customizable, and contextually driven static site using Next.js without duplicating content or copying assets.

Traditionally, creating digital exhibits applications required advanced technical experience and back-end infrastructure complexities. Canopy “makes easy” the creation of digital exhibits for libraries, archives, and museums by providing user-experience focused components which bring IIIF resources to life. Canopy provides a straightforward method to curate works from multiple sources and provide additional perspectives and context beyond included descriptive metadata. A rich viewing experience through a static site backed by the IIIF standard ensures accessibility with minimal cost and technical expertise.

This presentation will demonstrate the concept of a IIIF Collection, how to harness familiar Markdown syntax to effortlessly adapt Canopy UI components, and guide attendees through deploying and hosting their Canopy site. The presentation will give attendees the knowledge and autonomy required to effectively implement a Canopy generated static site for their specific use cases.

13:30 - 15:00	<p>Panel: The Evolving Role of Repositories in the Diamond OA Ecosystem Location: Brevsorterarsalen 2 Session Chair: Elizabeth Krznarich, DataCite</p>
	<p>ID: 331 / PAN02: 1 Panels Topics: Research Transparency, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement Keywords: diamond OA, overlay peer review</p> <p>The evolving role of repositories in the diamond OA ecosystem Kathleen Shearer¹, Eloy Rodrigues², Martin Klein⁴, Paul Walk³, Tamy Nakano¹ ¹COAR, The Netherlands; ²University of Minho, Portugal; ³Antleaf, UK; ⁴Los Alamos National Laboratory, US</p> <p>Repositories - together with external peer review services - offer a compelling new model for diamond OA, which could reduce both technical and cost burdens of publishing by distributing the publishing functions across different services. This interactive session will bring together several panelists to discuss the specific challenges for repositories in participating in the diamond ecosystem and document new functionalities that will be needed for repositories to support this new role. Audience participation will be encouraged during the session in order to hear the perspectives of members of the Open Repository community. The panel will also be an opportunity to provide input to the COAR Notify team about what resources would be helpful for the repository community in order to participate more fully in the diamond ecosystem.</p>
13:30 - 15:00	<p>Presentations: Elevating Underrepresented Voices Location: Brevsorterarsalen 3 Session Chair: Katarina Wiberg, National Library of Sweden</p>
	<p>ID: 164 / PR24: 1 Presentations Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability Keywords: Open Access Repositories, HBCU Scholarly Communication, Research Transparency, Digital Repository Management, Metadata</p> <p>Open Access Evolution: Empowering Research at a Historically Black College and University, United States Nurhak Tuncer Bayramli Elizabeth City State University, United States of America</p> <p>In this presentation, I will discuss the proactive steps taken by Elizabeth City State University's academic library to uphold our commitment to open access and amidst the phasing out of our current digital platform. While I will tell the journey of establishing the very first open access repository on our campus, the conversation will center on the exploration for robust alternative platforms and the pursuit of regional collaboration with other university libraries to ensure continuous access to diverse scholarly materials. A focused literature review will be conducted to pinpoint the gaps in existing research about open access dynamics within HBCU libraries. I will recount personal experiences from a five-year tenure managing an open access repository, with special attention to the inclusion and dissemination of non-traditional content such as music, videos, and multimedia. The discussion highlights the impact on scholarly communications and the advancement of research transparency within communities often left at the margins and underrepresented communities. The analysis accentuates the significant role that the open access repositories serve in broadening the scope of research visibility and its integration into the broader global academic discourse.</p>
	<p>ID: 321 / PR24: 2 Presentations Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement Keywords: Bureau, Kenya National Bureau of Statistics Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS) and Institutional repository</p> <p>ROLE OF NATIONAL STATISTICS REPOSITORY IN DATA AND STATISTICS MANAGEMENT: A DISSEMINATION TOOL TOWARDS ELEVATING UNDERREPRESENTED COMMUNITIES IN KENYA Jacqueline Dama Tundu Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, Kenya</p> <p>The proposal presents a background information about Kenya National Bureau of Statistics and the Bureau's Library. The Background information provides the legal framework and the mandate of the organization, including specific functions towards production, dissemination, use and publishing statistics. The proposal highlights the current situation of the library and the need for establishing an institutional repository for documentation, dissemination of data and statistical information resources. By establishing the IR, the Bureau will archive official statistics and other statistical intellectual products created by various communities. These materials will then be made accessible to end users both within and outside the organization. The repository's primary goal is to establish a national integrated one-stop data and statistics dissemination hub.</p>
	<p>ID: 391 / PR24: 3 Presentations Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement Keywords: Mapuche women, open repositories, indigenous people in Chile, Mapuche communities</p> <p>Conceptualization and development of an open repository on Mapuche women in southern Chile Jocelyn Patterson¹, Yohanna del Rio¹, Jorge Castillo^{1,2}, Martina Paillacar¹ ¹Fundacion Nutram, Chile; ²Universidad de La Frontera</p> <p>This proposal discusses the conceptualization and development of an open repository and a community for Mapuche women in southern Chile. The Mapuche people is 80.2 % of the native peoples in Chile. Indigenous women in Chile face various challenges, like income poverty, and difficulties for the preservation of their customs and traditions. This proposal aims to visibilize the different roles as leaders of Mapuche women. The work with the communities will adopt the Nütram methodology, which encourages sharing knowledge in a conversation where people get together and form a circle to talk to each other. The objective is to rescue the testimonies and the living memory of their ancestral practices. Moreover, we will speak about the development of an open repository that captures and preserves the heritage and scientific documentation on Mapuche women. The information sources to populate the repository come from scientific repositories, databases, and historical archives. The repository will generate an open virtual community of researchers that will contribute new digital content, making it a tool for the co-creation of knowledge for Mapuche women and researchers. This proposal will be part of the project funded by Invest in Open Infrastructure and will be carried out during 2024.</p>
	<p>ID: 253 / PR24: 4 Presentations Topics: Underrepresented Communities Keywords: Open Repositories, Marginalised Societies, Women Marketeers, Unrepresented Communities, Digital Repositories</p> <p>The Void of Open Repositories and Its Impact on Marginalised Societies: A Case of Women Marketeers in Makululu Compound, Kabwe, Zambia MPUNDU CHILONGA KWAME NKURUMAH UNIVERSITY, Zambia</p> <p>This paper investigates the profound consequences of the absence of open repositories on marginalised societies, focusing on Women Marketeers in Makululu Compound, Kabwe, Zambia, a region marked by limited digital access. As the second largest compound in Africa and extensively studied in Zambia, Makululu serves as a compelling case study. The paper adopts a qualitative approach to unveil the complex challenges faced by this community due to the lack of accessible digital platforms. The study exposes how this dearth negatively impacts education, economic opportunities, cultural preservation, and overall community empowerment. The findings underscore the intricate tapestry of challenges emanating from the unavailability of open repositories. Educational resources and skill development opportunities are compromised, contributing to economic disparities and hindering entrepreneurship. Moreover, the research highlights the broader implications for community empowerment, illustrating how the lack of open repositories impedes collaborative initiatives and knowledge-sharing within the community. The paper uncovers threats to cultural preservation, emphasizing how the absence of open repositories erodes traditional knowledge-sharing practices and stifles cultural expression. In response, the</p>

	paper advocates for strategies that promote equitable access to information, emphasizing the importance of digital inclusivity and open access initiatives in fostering empowerment, inclusion, and the preservation of cultural diversity.
15:00 - 15:30	Coffee Break
15:30 - 16:30	Panel: The Repository Rodeo Location: Drottningporten 1+2 Session Chair: Leigh Stork , University of Strathclyde
	<p>ID: 210 / PAN03: 1 Panels <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems <i>Keywords:</i> Dataverse, DSpace, EPrints, Fedora, InvenioRDM, Islandora, Samvera</p> <p>The Repository Rodeo Heather Greer Klein¹, Gustavo Durand², Rory McNicholl³, Arran Griffith⁴, Alex Ioannidis⁵, Kirsta Stapelfeldt⁶, Kristi Park⁷, Donald Moses⁸, Kate Dohe⁹</p> <p>¹Samvera, United States of America; ²Harvard University, United States of America; ³CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom; ⁴Lyrasis, United States of America; ⁵CERN, Switzerland; ⁶University of Toronto, Canada; ⁷Texas Digital Library, United States of America; ⁸University of Prince Edward Island, Canada; ⁹University of Maryland, United States of America</p> <p>The Repository Rodeo returns for another round of questions and answers! This popular panel, featured since Open Repositories 2016 in Dublin, offers a broad overview of repository platforms at Open Repositories and provides an opportunity for spirited discussion amongst panelists and attendees. Join community representatives from Dataverse, DSpace, EPrints, Fedora, InvenioRDM, Islandora, and Samvera as we briefly explain what each of our repositories actually does. We'll also talk about the directions of our respective technical and community developments and related to the conference theme of "Empowering Global Progress," we'll discuss the work our repository communities do to support research transparency, implement sustainable practices, and empower global progress.</p> <p>This panel will be a great opportunity for newcomers to Open Repositories to get a crash course on open repository options and to meet representatives from each of their communities. After a brief presentation from each representative, we'll open the session up for questions from the audience.</p>
16:30 - 19:00	Minute Madness, Poster Session & Welcome Reception Location: Drottningporten Session Chair: Joseph Kraus , Colorado School of Mines Session Chair: Jessica Byström , Chalmers University of Technology
	<p>ID: 291 / PS: 1 Posters <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> User Experience, Collaboration, Corporate Identity Alignment, Repository Design Enhancement</p> <p>Enhancing DSpace CRIS 7: An Approach to Repository Design Sumanghalyah Suntharam¹, Maja Eterovic¹, Domenico Zecchinelli², Dirk Verdicchio¹</p> <p>¹University of Bern; ²Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana, SUPSI</p> <p>University of Bern and Scuola universitaria professionale della Svizzera italiana, utilizing DSpace CRIS 7, are in the process of redesigning the user interface to enhance user-friendliness and engage a broader audience. Recognizing the default design's resemblance to traditional repositories, we address the need for a modern and appealing interface. Our methodology involves the creation of wireframes and work with a design company, aligning the entire process with our corporate identity. While results are yet to be implemented, the aim is a more engaging and transparent repository interface, reflecting modern design principles. The initiative responds to the evolving expectations of academic and public users, emphasizing user-friendliness, aesthetics, and transparency.</p> <p>This proposal seeks to share our ongoing experience and anticipated outcomes, aligning with the OR2024 sub-theme of "Transparency: Promoting research transparency" to contribute to discussions on enhancing the openness and accessibility of academic repositories.</p>
	<p>ID: 129 / PS: 2 Posters <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation <i>Keywords:</i> Research Data Management; Hyrax-Based Repository; Review Workflows; User Participation in Development; Neuroscience</p> <p>Fostering research transparency in neuroscience: Supporting the research data management lifecycle with a Hyrax-based research data repository Tobias Otto¹, Marlene Pacharra², Paul Walk³, Johannes Frenzel⁴, Nina Olivia Caroline Winter⁴</p> <p>¹Cognitive Psychology, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany; ²Biopsychology, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany, CRC 1280 „Extinction Learning“; ³Antleaf; ⁴IT.SERVICES, Ruhr University Bochum, Germany</p> <p>The poster showcases an ongoing adaptation of the open-source research data repository ReSeed, built in Samvera Hyrax 3 and operated by Ruhr University Bochum (Germany), to support day-to-day research data management in neuroscience. In collaboration with the interdisciplinary Collaborative Research Center (CRC) 1280 "Extinction Learning", which involves more than 70 researchers from four institutions, workflows have been developed that enable the ingest of research data and metadata at the early stages of research. User feedback drives ongoing optimization of the interface for efficient presentation of research data organized in a navigable, multi-level tree folder structure featuring expandable elements for nested data and metadata. A tailored three-level roles and rights system, aligned with the CRC's organizational structure, along with a faceted search functionality, is designed to promote early data sharing and collaboration. For sustainable research, the system incorporates three-stage quality control workflows for FAIR data publication and 10-year preservation. Ongoing improvements, driven by collaboration between CRC researchers, the central facility and external service providers, focus on the seamless integration of the system into the daily routine of researchers with the aim of improving transparency throughout the research process.</p>
	<p>ID: 282 / PS: 3 Posters <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Discoverability, indexing, scholarly search, harvesting, interoperability, aggregation, machine access</p> <p>US Repositories Network Discovery Pilot Petr Knoth¹, Kathleen Shearer², Paul Walk³, Matteo Cancellieri¹, David Pride¹, Tina Baich⁴, Heather Joseph⁴</p> <p>¹The Open University, United Kingdom; ²Confederation of Open Access Repositories; ³Antleaf Ltd.; ⁴SPARC</p> <p>This poster will highlight the critical need for building an interoperable US repository network as a foundation of a national research infrastructure. The US Repository Network (USRN) is launching a pilot project to facilitate the discoverability of USRN resources and to investigate its role in ensuring free and equitable access to federally funded research as required by the OSTP Memorandum. The project is a collaboration of SPARC, COAR, Antleaf and CORE. It involves indexing metadata and full texts from participating repositories for discovery, assessing and improving current practices, and enhancing metadata quality. The initiative, supported by 20 diverse high-profile repositories, will provide best practice guidelines for both machine and human discoverability of research articles.</p>
	<p>ID: 248 / PS: 4 Posters <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency <i>Keywords:</i> Institutional repositories, Data protection, Health data, Sensitive medical data</p> <p>How to be open with sensitive data – examples from the KI data repository project Helena Eckerbom, Karin Widin, Helena Skyllberg, Glenn Haya, Lisa Andersson Karolinska Institutet, Sweden</p>

The poster shows the current state of challenges related to sharing and publishing sensitive medical data, our experience so far, challenges we are facing and potential future solutions.

The project "KI Data Repository - Phase 1" is one of Swedish National Data Services (SND's) currently four Flagship projects (SND, 2023), which means that the project's results are expected to be of benefit to all higher education institutions within the SND network that do not yet have, or are about to arrange a local solution for storing research data to be made available through SND's research data catalogue. As a Flagship project, "KI Data Repository - Phase 1" reports to SND and is running during fall 2023-until the end of 2024.

ID: 161 / PS: 5

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems

Keywords: disciplinary repository, data sharing, sharing level, reviewer link

PsychArchives, the Disciplinary Repository for Psychological Science

Lea Gerhards, Yi-Hsiu Chen, Anne Königs, Marie-Luise Müller, Robert Studtrucker, Martin Kock, Christiane Baier, Peter Weiland

Leibniz Institute for Psychology (ZPID), Germany

PsychArchives, the disciplinary repository for psychological science, supports the publication of a range of digital research object types, including articles, preregistrations, research data, code, and tests. Committed to the FAIR principles, its aim is to enable researchers to comply with good scientific practice standards of openness and transparency. The repository is provided as a non-commercial public service by the Leibniz Institute for Psychology (ZPID), the supra-regional scientific research support organization for psychology in German-speaking countries.

A key feature of PsychArchives is its Sharing Level concept, addressing researchers' diverse needs when sharing their research output by allowing them nuanced control over access and usage of their content. The currently implemented Sharing Levels range from open to restricted access, each with tailored licensing. Another important feature is the reviewer link functionality that allows contributors to share DROs anonymously before publication to support the peer-review process.

The technical base of PsychArchives is DSpace with a PHP/Symfony frontend and in-house developed components for submitting and delivering content. PsychArchives is committed to efficiently and securely archiving and publishing psychological research within a robust digital infrastructure.

ID: 185 / PS: 6

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: persistent identifiers, metadata, DOIs, DataCite

Ready to ROR: Planning for research organization identifiers in the Carolina Digital Repository

Anna Goslen, Rebekah Kati

University Libraries, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, United States of America

The Carolina Digital Repository (CDR) is planning an implementation of Research Organization Registry (ROR) identifiers in our institutional repository, with the goals of unambiguously identifying Works affiliated with our institution in DataCite as well as improving funder metadata in our local system to better support funder requirements. Our poster will provide a brief introduction to ROR, describe the impetus for exploring ROR at the CDR, and outline how the CDR currently uses persistent identifiers. We'll explain the proposal we developed for integrating ROR into the repository, the resources and other implementations that were referenced, the problems we are hoping to solve, and next steps for implementation.

ID: 234 / PS: 7

Posters

Topics: Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: standardization, openness, sustainability, interoperability

The Community-Based DINI Certificate for Open Access Publication Services - 20 Years of Self-Empowerment through Standards

Pascal-Nicolas Becker², Daniel Beucke³, Ute Blumtritt⁴, Isabella Meinecke¹, Jochen Schirrwagen⁵, Thomas Severiens⁶

¹Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg, Germany; ²The Library Code, Germany; ³Georg-August-Universität Göttingen, Germany;

⁴Universitätsbibliothek Chemnitz, Germany; ⁵RWTH Aachen University, Germany; ⁶Jade Hochschule Wilhelmshaven, Oldenburg, Elsfleth, Germany

For 20 years, the German DINI Certificate for Open Access Publication Services has provided transparent criteria and guidelines for building and maintaining trustworthy publication services such as repositories and Diamond Open Access journals. The community-developed, non-commercial certificate paves the way for open scholarly communication and supports the prerequisites for the free availability of scholarly information as an essential element of future-oriented research-related services. Introduced in 2004 and now in its 7th revised version, the DINI Certificate has been used in approximately 120 - mostly successful - certification processes. Since the beginning the catalogue takes into account international standards (e.g. provided by COAR, OpenAIRE). With this poster, we are reaching out to the international repository community by illustrating the key features of the well-established Certificate and its catalogue of criteria. The latest version of the Certificate has been adapted to the Austrian legal system. We hope that other countries will follow, so that repositories in more countries can benefit from the DINI Certificate.

ID: 141 / PS: 8

Posters

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems

Keywords: Digital Scholarly Editions, Repositories, FAIR principles

Unlocking the Potential of Digital Scholarly Editions: Strategies for Attracting the DH Community to Utilize Repositories

Kathleen Neumann¹, Robert Stephan²

¹Verbundzentrale des GBV (VZG), Germany; ²Rostock University Library, Germany

A variety of software products are used for the collection and presentation of digital scholarly editions. In our view, repositories already provide many important functionalities for this purpose. We will develop concepts and strategies based on the open-source repository framework MyCoRe to make these advantages accessible to the Digital Humanities (DH) community and to make the use of repositories in the context of digital scholarly edition projects more attractive. An important objective is that the repository is actively used during the creation process of the edition and can thus be used as a tool for collaboration.

Individual project examples are used to examine both the possibilities of data ingestion using standardized metadata formats and the integration of existing services such as TEI tools and authority data services. The poster showcases a visual representation, featuring an infrastructure sketch and data flow diagram, illustrating the interaction of TEI tools and repositories. Through this, we highlight the pathway toward structured and schema-compliant data entry for digital scholarly editions. Our presentation seeks to inspire a dialogue on how these strategies can contribute to the broader goal of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices in Digital Humanities.

ID: 339 / PS: 9

Posters

Topics: Repository Systems

Keywords: application repository, data science app sharing, machine learning model sharing

Building a repository of data science and machine learning applications

Arnold Kochari

SciLifeLab, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

As an increasingly large number of research projects produces machine learning models and data science applications a need arises for storing and sharing these research outputs, just like in case of e.g., produced research data. To meet this need, we built a custom repository focused specifically on sharing machine learning models and data science applications (SciLifeLab Serve, <https://serve.scilifelab.se>); it is currently available to life science researchers affiliated with Swedish research institutions. Our repository goes beyond just sharing files or code – users can make inferences using the submitted models and can interact with the submitted

data science applications. At the same time, each submission is an entry with accompanying metadata. Our aim is to allow researchers to share their models and applications through an intuitive web interface and while doing so meet FAIR requirements. The service has components and, therefore, accompanying challenges of both a hosting platform and a research data repository. The developed platform is available as open source software that others are welcome to use to launch their own instances. In this poster we will share our journey so far, challenges, and how we met them.

ID: 244 / PS: 10

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency

Keywords: Electronic Laboratory Notebooks, ELN, Repositories, Data Life Cycle

Connecting ELN to Repositories – connecting daily work to long-term transparency

Juliane Jacob

Universität Hamburg, Germany

At Universität Hamburg the Center for sustainable Research Data Management offers a variety of services along the data life cycle - starting with data management plans and going on with a repository service. One service, which is in between and especially needed in the natural science, is an electronic laboratory notebook software. elabFTW works in the department of chemistry, however, at least one more open source software (e.g. chemotion) will be established for the university in 2024. The ELNs will directly be connected to the repository. The integration of ELNs to repositories offers several advantages. Firstly, it enables seamless data sharing and collaboration among researchers. Researchers can easily upload, store, and share their experimental data, making it accessible to their colleagues, collaborators, and even the broader scientific community. This not only promotes transparency but also facilitates data reuse and reproducibility, thus enhancing the overall research output and impact. Secondly, ELNs connected to repositories provide a secure and organized storage solution for research data. Researchers can confidently store and manage their valuable data, knowing that it is well-preserved and protected against loss or corruption.

The poster reports the ongoing work and learnings of the ELN implementation and connection to the repository.

ID: 318 / PS: 11

Posters

Topics: Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: metadata, Dublin Core, scholarly resources, academic repositories

DC-SRAP: Metadata Application Profile for Academic Repositories

Osma Suominen

National Library of Finland, Finland

Dublin Core metadata is commonly used for the description of doctoral dissertations, Master's theses, article preprints, technical reports and other resources created in institutions of higher education such as universities and polytechnics, for storing and making them available via their institutional repositories. DC Metadata Terms do not contain all core metadata elements required for the description of these materials. Therefore many local extensions to Dublin Core have been created, on national, regional and institutional levels.

In order to make Dublin Core better suited for the description of scholarly works, the Scholarly Resources Application Profile (SRAP) is being developed in a DCMI working group. The application profile will include guidance and examples of how to use Dublin Core, along with other metadata vocabularies such as BIBO, to describe scholarly resources. The working group will also propose additions to Dublin Core Terms to better match the requirements of metadata for scholarly resources.

The poster will present the current draft of the SRAP profile and how to apply it for different types of scholarly documents. When completed, SRAP will improve the interoperability, discoverability and transparency of academic institutional repositories. Parts of SRAP may be applied also to other types of repositories.

ID: 218 / PS: 12

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: Research Transparency, Long-term Preservation, Islandora, Open Digital Repositories

Enhancing Research through Open Digital Repositories in University Libraries—A Case Study of Peking University Library

Chao Sun¹, Zhenxin Wu², Yunhai Tong¹, Hanyu Li²

¹Peking University, China; ²National Science Library, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China

This poster discusses how university libraries can enhance the visibility of academic research and promote interdisciplinary cooperation through the management of faculty and student research materials via open digital repositories. Taking the construction of the open digital repository at Peking University Library as an example, this paper studies the implementation path of open digital repository in university libraries from two aspects: fundamental platform construction and management mechanisms. Finally, we emphasize the role of university construction of open digital repositories in promoting transparency, accessibility, and cooperation.

ID: 306 / PS: 13

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: ETDs, Reference Lists, DataCite

Ideas Challenge Update: Surfacing Thesis and Dissertation Reference Lists through Institutional Repositories

Esther Jackson¹, Fred Duby¹, Daryl Grenz², Rawan Karsou²

¹Columbia University Libraries, United States of America; ²King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST)

This poster will present an in-progress update on the work done around the 2022 Open Repositories Ideas Challenge, Surfacing Thesis and Dissertation Reference Lists through Institutional Repositories. We are interested in sharing our work thus far, and hearing feedback from attendees about our methodology as we continue this work.

Researchers often discover relevant content in part by navigating the network of relationships (especially citations) between research outputs, and tools to support this are built into many scholarly databases and services. These systems either use structured citation information provided by the authors or publisher of an item, or extract this information directly from its full text. Historically, the ability to reuse citation information outside of a specific system has been limited. However, in recent years a dramatic shift has taken place in the treatment of citation information from publications such as journal articles through the Initiative for Open Citations (I4OC) and the resultant increase in the quantity and level of openness of reference information deposited by publishers with Crossref.

We will introduce the workflows trialed at our two universities to obtain, store, display, and disseminate (through DataCite metadata) the reference lists from ETDs in our institutional repositories, including unexpected roadblocks.

ID: 184 / PS: 14

Posters

Topics: Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Java libraries, library metadata, metadata management

LibMeta - Java Object Models for Common Library Metadata Standards

Robert Stephan

Rostock University Library, Germany

High quality metadata are essential for the presentation, accessibility, discoverability, and preservation of cultural objects. Processing metadata has become an important task in cultural heritage institutions.

On this poster we present a set of Java libraries, that provide a uniform approach to the creation and processing of metadata objects in one of the following widely-used standards: METS, MODS, MARC, PICA, DublinCore, ALTO.

For each standard a corresponding Java object model was developed. JAXB annotations (JAVA API for XML-Binding) are used for XML-based standards (e.g. METS, MODS) to specify the mapping between Java object model and XML representation. The JSON Binding API is used for the serialization and deserialization of metadata objects which have a JSON-based representation (like MARC or PICA).

Consistently implemented processor classes allow reading and writing data from file, URL, input stream or string. Builder classes following the Builder Design Pattern can be used to create and modify metadata objects in a very elaborated way. Validator classes check XML data against the corresponding XML schemas.

Furthermore some source code examples will demonstrate how attendees can use and integrate the tools into their own software.

ID: 316 / PS: 16

Posters

Topics: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: SDGs, visualization, search strategies, research trends, indexing, institutional repositories

Showcasing research related to the SDG's using the local repository: the case of Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences

Daniel Albertsson, Tomas Lundén, Ylva Toljander

Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden

This poster proposal describes an initiative undertaken by the Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU), to map their scientific output with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). SLU wanted to assess its contributions to the SDGs and also to aim to understand its focus and impact on specific SDGs. Given that the SDG's are not intended to be used for subject indexing of individual scholarly articles, but rather are politically motivated, different interpretations arise during the SDG classification of scholarly articles, leading to diverse results across approaches.

SLU has adopted a customized approach, utilizing its local repository (SLUpub) to index publications with SDG data. Librarians manually screen search results, comparing article titles and abstracts with individual SDG targets, sub-targets, and indicators. The indexing process involves manual input, limited to three SDGs per publication. The resulting SDG data is showcased on a dedicated web page and integrated into SLUpub's web interface. Although the current process relies on English language articles and major commercial databases, future plans include expanding to cover Swedish articles and grey literature, with the repository as the primary source. The poster illustrates the indexing process and visualizations of SLU's contributions to the SDGs.

ID: 399 / PS: 17

Posters

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Digital accessibility, institutional repositories, institutional policies

Enhancing Inclusivity: Digital Accessibility and the Institutional Repository

Anne Shelley

Iowa State University, United States of America

Accessibility of institutional repositories (IRs)—the content made available, repository platforms themselves, and related websites—is an important but often unprioritized issue in IR management. In this poster I will cover efforts to evaluate and enhance the digital accessibility of Iowa State University's Digital Repository. The motivation for this work is to comply with an institutional policy affecting public-facing web page content and online courses; the policy's timeline began in 2022 and asks staff to meet benchmarks leading up to full compliance by July 1, 2026. I will share strategies taken, challenges encountered, decisions taken, and details of conversations with stakeholders inside and outside the library. This poster will be of interest to repository managers who wish to improve the accessibility of their repositories

ID: 131 / PS: 18

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: E-accessibility, repository, open access, research data management

Access for All - How do I make my repository accessible?

Susanne Blumesberger, Maria Guseva, Sonja Edler, Victoria Eisenheld

University of Vienna

Repositories are an important part of research data management, enabling the sustainable and free use of data. To ensure that these data can be used by as many people as possible, repositories must be designed to be as accessible as possible. Several components need to be considered. Access to the repository needs to be as easy as possible; logging in and searching should not be a barrier. The objects themselves should be designed to be as accessible as possible, e.g. images should have meaningful captions, videos should be accompanied by text, text should be designed accordingly, and so on. The descriptions of the objects, the metadata, must also be easy to read for everyone. All help texts, explanations, and guidelines must also meet accessibility criteria. Last but not least, the upload process must be designed in such a way that it can be carried out by anyone. The poster aims to show how repositories can be made more accessible, thereby supporting open access and enabling everyone to be an independent scholar. The individual aspects of an accessible repository will be shown and explained.

ID: 362 / PS: 19

Posters

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: Current research information systems (CRIS), Bibliometrics, Performance-Based Research Fund (PBRF)

Institutional Repository KTISIS: Research Evaluation and Promotion Tool

Marios Zervas¹, Petros Artemi¹, George Veranis²

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The continuous development of the KTISIS institutional repository and the constant adaptation of its services to the needs of the Cyprus University of Technology (CUT) following the international trends and perspectives make KTISIS a pioneer in the world of institutional repositories. KTISIS allows researchers to include their research activities in their repository account. The adoption of a Performance-Based Research Fund (PBRF) by the University for the funding of researchers through criteria related to their activities and the new functionality allowing them through a bibliometric tool to generate their CV based on the Cyprus Quality Assurance and Accreditation Agency for Higher Education (CYQAA) standard make KTISIS a tool for their evaluation and promotion. KTISIS shows the metrics of research impact from various bibliographic databases and the alternative impact of research on the Social Network, thus providing researchers and authorities with a direct insight into research interest worldwide, giving them the opportunity to react and increase interest and opportunities for future collaborations. The article highlights all the efforts of the CUT Library to enhance research and assist its community in its efforts to promote research and find new opportunities for future collaborations.

ID: 203 / PS: 20

Posters

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Research data management, Machine-actionable data management plans, CRIS integration, FAIR

Machine actionable DMPs in practice : making a FAIR difference at Chalmers

Urban Andersson, Jeremy Azzopardi, Maria Kinger

Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden

Data management planning is a key task and an essential element in the process to manage the whole FAIR data life cycle. It is also a mandatory requirement from several major funders, as well as some research organizations, including Chalmers. Yet writing and updating a data management plan - even with the support of a DMP system - is often considered a rather tedious task that, despite the intentions, in the end often fails to return any substantial added value, other than policy compliance, for either researchers or other parties involved.

By automating central workflows and involving key stakeholders in that process we have found that it is quite possible to accomplish a solution that not only facilitates the researcher tasks, but also ensures controlled, re-usable metadata and enables central stakeholders to be automatically connected with relevant parts of the process, from planning to sharing and preservation of data. Using the DMP tool Data Stewardship Wizard, funder project databases and not at least the locally developed CRIS system (research.chalmers.se) and supporting routines, the first steps were implemented in our production workflows (in 2022).

This poster presents both the work done so far, as well as planned future developments.

ID: 169 / PS: 22

Posters

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Preserving Heritage, Sharing Repository, Data equity, Open repository Nigeria

Preserving and Sharing Nigeria's Heritage: The National Repository of Nigeria

Chinwe Veronica Anunobi, Chukwuemeka Kelvin Udoji

National Library of Nigeria, Nigeria

The National Library of Nigeria (NLN) faces the critical challenge of preserving and disseminating Nigeria's rich but aging heritage. Preservation deploying technology is often hindered by limited resources. The inaccessibility of these heritage creates a knowledge gap within Nigeria, limiting research and understanding of the country's history and culture. The National Repository of Nigeria (NRN), deployed by the National Library, tackles this issue by actively harvesting and uploading digitized historical resources in the National Repository. Despite limited resources, the project has already begun preserving and showcasing this vital heritage. Over 650 resources have so far been digitized and uploaded, making them accessible to Nigerians and the global community for the first time. This not only safeguards these fragile materials but also empowers research, education, and cultural exchange. The National Repository of Nigeria stands as a beacon of hope for preserving and unlocking Nigeria's immense cultural wealth. By providing open access to most of these resources, the project empowers Nigerians and the world to connect with their heritage and forge a brighter future informed by the past.

ID: 396 / PS: 23

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: REST API; IIIF; OCR; microservices; Institutional Repository;

The Road From DSpace 6 to DSpace 7 and Beyond: Building (and Building on) Two Modern Digital Repositories at Rice University

Ying Jin, John Mulligan, Kenneth Evans

Rice University, United States of America

In October 2023, the Digital Scholarship Services team in Fondren Library at Rice University upgraded its digital repository. The process was both challenging, rewarding, and instructive for our future work on digital collections. We took a mixed approach in which 27% of our content was moved to Quartex, which could be curated as digital cultural heritage, 11% was retired, and the remainder migrated from the DSpace 6.4 system to the new 7.6 deployment. We are now using our two new platforms' APIs to enable a microservices-based approach to customized UI presentations for special collections, and semi-automatic metadata enrichment, and document submission workflows. This poster describes our preliminary attempts in this space on two collections: geo-located photographs of Chinese subway advertisements over two decades and the geographically dispersed papers relating to the United States' President's Council of Advisors on Science and Technology.

ID: 270 / PS: 24

Posters

Topics: Climate Justice, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Research themes, curated collections, SOLR indexing, public engagement, institutional repositories

Oxford University Research Archive (ORA) – themed 'Collections'

Jason Partridge

University of Oxford, United Kingdom

Many areas of research are undertaken at the University of Oxford. ORA Collections aim to bring content available in the repository, covering specific themes of research, together in to a single presentable and searchable space; showcasing all types of work (articles, conference papers, book sections, theses, data, etc.) together for engagement and reference.

To avoid manual curation of content for an ORA Collection, SOLR queries have been used to present a work within a theme. This has involved development of SOLR join queries and targeted field indexing to refine search results to the relevance of a collection theme.

Three collections have been launched so far, focusing on research themes of COVID-19, Climate, and Artificial Intelligence research. With the creation of each collection the mechanism for curating and presenting results have been developed and refined. The collections have been well received so far with the Climate Research Collection being shortlisted as a finalist in the Green Gown Awards in association with UKRI.

We hope that the work done with ORA will provide inspiration to others in presenting themed research collections as well as being able to share the development with SOLR queries. Further reading at: <https://ora.ox.ac.uk/objects/uuid:5c46148d-6739-4865-bae7-08fe7af87d24>

ID: 146 / PS: 25

Posters

Topics: Responsible Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI), Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Large language models (LLMs), LangChain, Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), Natural language processing (NLP), DSpace

Querying DSpace: An AI Powered Conversation Application using RAG with Langchain

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¹University of Oklahoma, United States of America; ²University of Oregon, United States of America

AI has the potential to significantly impact open access repository development landscape in various ways like enabling better search, content recommendation, identifying new patterns in scholarly content, and promoting openness in datasets and content. Large language models (LLMs) have emerged as crucial and widely used resources in the field of natural language processing, which is a subfield of artificial intelligence (AI) and shares common ground with machine learning (ML). LLMs allow computers to comprehend and produce text in a manner that resembles human communication.

Our goal during the experiment was to create a conversation application that integrates OpenAI to query DSpace using natural language processing (NLP). We explored technologies such as LLMs, OpenAI API, LangChain, embeddings, and vector stores. LLMs are deep learning models trained on large datasets. The OpenAI API provides a cloud interface for accessing OpenAI's machine learning models. LangChain is an AI framework for language-based applications. Embeddings encode information in high-dimensional vector spaces. Vector stores are databases that store vector embeddings of non-numerical data. To create better responses, we used retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to incorporate additional, real-time data from DSpace. This allows us to explore the most up-to-date data in DSpace.

ID: 322 / PS: 26

Posters

Topics: Repository Systems

Keywords: ORCID, DSpace, DSpace-CRIS

The ORCID integration into DSpace and DSpace-CRIS

Oliver Goldschmidt

TU Hamburg, Germany

PIDs like ORCID or DOI can be considered as the probably most important pillars to empower global progress to repository systems. Today any repository software should have a working ORCID integration to help the users to distinguish persons on a global level and another persistent identifier to address publications.

The well-known repository software DSpace has a working integration of ORCID, which has been introduced in DSpace 7.3 (June 2022). But even in the currently latest version DSpace 7.6 it's still not complete.

DSpace-CRIS is a software, which is very much tied to DSpace, but it's a standalone software and an institution has to choose whether to use DSpace or DSpace-CRIS. DSpace-CRIS is maintained and developed by 4Science and is containing a complete ORCID integration for a long time.

Hamburg University of Technology recently conducted a project in cooperation with 4Science, which was funded by ORCID in context of the Global Participation Fund. The project had the goal to improve the login process against ORCID for DSpace-CRIS.

This poster will illustrate the ORCID integrations of DSpace and DSpace-CRIS, focusing on the results of the login improvement project.

ID: 197 / PS: 28

Posters

Topics: Climate Justice, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Open Access, Open Science, Regulation, Standards

Policies and Practices for Sustainable Preservation of Theses and Dissertations in Institutional Repositories

Michael Boock¹, Behrooz Rasuli², Joachim Schöpfel³, Brenda Van Wyk⁴

¹Oregon State University; ²Iranian Research Institute for Information Science and Technology (IranDoc), Iran, Islamic Republic of; ³University of Lille; ⁴The University of Pretoria

Over the past two decades, higher education institutions (HEIs) have increasingly embraced digital formats for their theses and dissertations (TDs), aiming to improve their accessibility, dissemination, and impact. As a result, millions of TDs are available online through institutional repositories (IRs). As the shift towards digital repositories gains momentum, the enduring accessibility and secure archiving of university TDs within IRs necessitate robust policies and practices for digital preservation. This study will analyze the current global landscape of digital preservation policies and practices within the context of TDs, identify areas for improvement and potential gaps, and provide insights to enhance preservation strategies for these scholarly works in IRs. Focusing on a random sample of diverse IRs, this study utilizes content analysis to extract tacit knowledge from the written policies of HEIs around the world. The study will delve into the nuances of these policies, examining the extent to which they cover the preservation aspects of TDs, the specific measures outlined, and how they address relevant challenges. By conducting this analysis, the study seeks to provide insights for IRs managers, librarians, and stakeholders involved in the maintenance of IRs. The findings will contribute to enhancing the longevity and accessibility of HEIs' scholarly output.

ID: 116 / PS: 29

Posters

Topics: Underrepresented Communities

Keywords: accessibility, education and training, files, theses

Accessibility of theses. Are the guidelines enough?

Merja Riitta Kallio

University of Vaasa, Finland

The aim is to compare the accessibility of the theses stored in Osuva publications archive in 2019 and 2023 in the open collection of master's theses. In 2019, the University's general writing guidelines were introduced, but a transition period from the old guidelines was still in force. The old guidelines did not take accessibility into account in any way. The new guidelines contain accessibility guidelines. In the discussions, the universities' policy on the interpretation of the law is often invoked, with the university being responsible for providing the accessible template and instructions, but the creation of the file being the responsibility of the student. This study provides insight into whether this policy is sufficient to improve the accessibility of theses. Can we see any improvement?

ID: 390 / PS: 30

Posters

Topics: Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: web development, open source tools

Community websites made easy: a static website and headless CMS for Samvera.org

Heather Greer Klein¹, Adam Joseph Arling²

¹Samvera, United States of America; ²Northwestern University, United States of America

The Samvera.org website is the first place to look when learning who the Samvera community is, what the open repository technologies do, and how these different options might meet a given use case. Over the past ten years the website has been hosted on different platforms and fallen under the responsibilities of various volunteers, but the community has struggled to keep the site up to date and to share the broadest and most relevant Samvera technology implementations and examples.

Beginning in 2023, the samvera.org website and related subdomains have begun a transition to open-source GitHub apps, using NextJS and headless CMS Contentful to create fast, static sites hosted with GitHub pages. This new approach results in a web presence that is more accessible, sustainable, and transparent. Hosting on GitHub eliminates hosting and software costs and is open source and accessible. All the data that is most important to potential users, such as details about global implementations and blog posts with the latest Community news, is easily kept up to date by multiple volunteers with no technical expertise required. And when technologies change, the entire site and all the content can easily be moved to another hosting option.

ID: 109 / PS: 31

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems

Keywords: Research Data Management Repository, repository configuration

Out-of-the-Box Repository Configuration: Supporting Small-Scale Research Community Visibility and Transparency

Hagen Peukert

Universität Hamburg, Germany

Configuring a repository software often is a time-consuming process for non-experts. Yet for experts, the integration of a repository in the infrastructure of the institution becomes a challenge as many documented cases prove. The institutional single-sign-on system can be configured in a variety of ways. Linking the repository to the storage system may turn into an even more demanding issue. In addition, some researchers need highly customized data models. At the end, such problems may lead to compromise solutions, in which the data is de facto neither transparent nor in favor of underrepresented communities. Although (technically) the data itself is open access and available, it is hard to access, that is, usage incommensurable is a barrier to accessing the data. We like to present our experiences with Invenio-RDM, a turn-key research data management repository platform, (which is about to be rolled out and) which lowers configuration costs and diminishes false compromise solutions.

ID: 115 / PS: 32

Posters

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems

Keywords: Assessment, Digital Image Collections, Digital Public Goods

Assessment of Selected U.S. Digital Image Collections to Digital Public Goods Alliance's Standard

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This poster will discuss the researchers' assessment of whether selected U.S. digital image repositories align with the Digital Public Goods (DPGs) Alliance's DPGs Standard. It will share the current progress of this assessment, including their methodology and any results to date, as well as outline some initial considerations for practitioners. This research is unique because it (a) applies the DPGs Alliance's standards to U.S. digital collection image repositories, one distinct subset of the digital repository landscape assessed by the DPGs Alliance, and (b) contributes to the greater scholarly dialogue on digital collection image repositories as a public good.

ID: 148 / PS: 33

Posters

Topics: Underrepresented Communities

Keywords: Gə'əz manuscript, Gə'əz manuscripts inventory, Eritrean monasteries and churches, Conservation of manuscripts

The challenge of preserving Gə'əz manuscripts in Eritrea

Kiflom Michael Kahsay

Eritrean Research and Documentation Centre, Eritrea

Eritrea is rich with ancient manuscripts written with its own script known "Gə'əz". The script is an earliest one commonly found at both Eritrea and Ethiopia. Gə'əz could only be read by few people at

	<p>monasteries and churches. Today, these materials are far from rich of the common society and scholars with the exception of few monks and priests. Due to continuous use and handling, the age and intellectual contents of these materials are highly at risk. In unpublished preliminary study conducted by the Eritrean Research Documentation Centre (RDC) reveals that there are around 6042 registered manuscripts. However, all the interviewees confirm that the number of manuscripts would go beyond 20,000 if a holistic inventory is undertaken across the country. Yet, the country is unable to conduct a comprehensive and conclusive inventory of manuscripts and as a consequence, it became impossible to understand the extent and intellectual content of Gə'əz manuscripts. These realities became among the other reasons for not taking a serious conservation and preservation work on the ground and far more hindered the accessibility of these materials for scholarship. The purpose of this research was to suggest possible ways on how to preserve and prepare these collections ready for</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 409 / PS: 34 Posters <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> long-term project/collection, international authorship, sustainable growth</p> <p>The Long and Winding Road: Sustaining the Course of a Long Term Collection Project Kyle Lynn Bachman-Johnson University of Kentucky, United States of America</p> <p>I will share a case study highlighting the building of an international conference collection over the last 5 years, in the University of Kentucky's repository, a project that has changed course over the last year.</p> <p>Repository managers in Universities are often faced with competing demands for their services when it comes to collection development, necessitating creativity and agility. Many contributors require assistance with depositing work : This can involve digitization, collecting and curating, and other time intensive activities. This IR Manager came on board after the previous manager had undertaken to provide IR access to 100 years of events: The International Grassland Congress. Unquestionably a worthwhile collection, internationally created and utilized, I pursued ways to sustain and maximize our progress without allowing it to monopolize our limited resources.</p> <p>It's helpful to see the impact of the collection, its growth over time, and its reach: With a soil science focus, users in 236 countries and international authors it is a great example of transparency, community and sustainability.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 274 / PS: 35 Posters <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Information exposure, findability, connectivity, guidelines</p> <p>Exposing repository information to foster connections and trust: evaluating and implementing guidelines. Maaïke Lisanne Verburg¹, Michael Priddy¹, Hervé L'Hours², Robert Huber³, Robert Ulrich⁴, Ingrid Dillo¹, Joy Davidson⁵, Charlotte Neidiger⁴, Linda Reijnhoudt¹, Gabriela Meijas⁶, Parham Ramezani⁷ ¹Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), Netherlands, The; ²UK Data Service; ³University of Bremen - PANGAEA; ⁴Karlsruhe Institute of Technology; ⁵Digital Curation Centre; ⁶DataCite; ⁷LifeWatch ERIC</p> <p>FAIR-IMPACT is developing guidelines and a prototype to expose relevant information as metadata to facilitate discovery, provide context, support interoperability, and create a sense of trust in service providers and the services they offer. Transparent and linked information between objects, the repositories that hold or interact with them, and the registries and portals that use this information, can be indexed, harvested, reused, and potentially validated against agreed criteria or by designated validation authorities to improve collaboration and trust between stakeholders. The guidelines and technical implementation of them are intended to flexibly fit different use cases and scenarios that occur in the research data landscape, which is why we collect community input during the development of them. This input will directly feed into next iterations of the work.</p>
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Date: Wednesday, 05/June/2024

<p>08:30 - 17:00</p>	<p>Registration</p>
<p>09:00 - 10:30</p>	<p>24x7: Harnessing Collaborations for Development Location: Drottningporten 1 Session Chair: Ianthe Sutherland, University of Edinburgh</p>
	<p>ID: 111 / 24X702: 1 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Repository management, product development, user empowerment, repository tools and policies</p> <p>Empowering DSpace users and administrators: What is being done and where do we continue from here? Tal Ayalon World Bank, United States of America</p> <p>User empowerment has been one of the key areas of focus recommended in a report by the Product Visioning Working Group, which is part of the DSpace Leadership Group run by Lyrasis. The Working Group put an emphasis on enabling DSpace users to get more out of their repositories while avoiding outsourcing functions to a vendor or hiring a technical expert. In this session I will demonstrate how the World Bank implements end-user empowering functionality, as well as repository management empowerment measures, present and future.</p>
	<p>ID: 121 / 24X702: 2 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> DiVA repository, Consortium run repository, History of repository, Sweden</p> <p>The history of the DiVA repository: through the lens of being a consortium Petra Thorsson, Sara Tobiasson Uppsala University Library, Sweden</p> <p>DiVA is the largest repository in Sweden for publications with 50 members and it is unique since it is run as a consortium. Since 2001 DiVA has provided its members with a structure for publishing their publications in a reliable manner. This presentation will focus on the history of DiVA from its start as a project to host PhD thesis at Uppsala university to the system it is today, through the lens of being a consortium. DiVA is a collaborative repository where each member has a stake in the development of the system. From the early days where there were few members and often direct contact, to 2008 when the system was updated and the members increased and there was need for more formalized governing structures. DiVA has continued to be run as a consortium, which has greatly benefited the system and our members, allowing for insight and a stake in development of the system. Currently DiVA is developing its next phase and both management and members see the benefits from the consortium model.</p>
	<p>ID: 175 / 24X702: 3 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Digital Preservation Policy, Archivematica, Digitization, Heterogenic collections.</p> <p>Digital preservation of health cultural collections: the experience of the Oswaldo Cruz Foundation Marcus Vinicius Pereira-Silva¹, João Guilherme Nogueira Machado², Karina Veras Praxedes dos Santos¹, Vanessa de Arruda Jorge³, Marcos José de Araújo Pinheiro¹, Luciana Monteiro-Krebs¹ ¹Oswaldo Cruz Foundation, Casa de Oswaldo Cruz, Brazil; ²Oswaldo Cruz Foundation, Instituto de Comunicação e Informação Científica e Tecnológica em Saúde, Brazil; ³Oswaldo Cruz Foundation, Vice-Presidência de Educação, Informação e Comunicação,</p>

	<p>Brazil</p> <p>The Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Fiocruz), a Brazilian public health institute manages a wide range of collections, including research data, archival, bibliographic, museological, architectural, urbanistic and archaeological, and biological. In 2018, Fiocruz implemented the Preservation Policy for Scientific and Cultural Collections, aiming to improve access and preservation of its collections. Specifically focusing on digital preservation, Fiocruz formed a dedicated working group to develop the Fiocruz Digital Preservation Program. This program advocates compliance with the OAIS and establishes a basic framework that all collections must incorporate into their digital preservation plans. Fiocruz selected Archivematica as the digital preservation repository due to its integration capabilities with Fiocruz access platforms. The participatory model employed for policy and program implementation in digital preservation has proven effective. It has raised awareness among stakeholders and facilitated alignment of knowledge and transparency. The lessons learnt by Fiocruz in the digital preservation repository implementation process serves as a valuable example for similar institutions in Latin America and Caribbean (LAC) and other regions, highlighting the importance of collaborative efforts in implementing digital preservation strategies.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 181 / 24X702: 4 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> DSpace 7, communication, outreach, relationships</p> <p>Using a DSpace 7 Upgrade as an Outreach Opportunity Colleen Lyon University of Texas at Austin, United States of America</p> <p>Repositories with policies that allow users to submit content may save time in processing submissions, but do introduce issues with maintaining lines of communication with all submitters. As repositories grow in size, keeping track of all individuals and units who are using the repository can become difficult. Repository managers need to balance the frequency and length of communication in order to not overwhelm or annoy recipients. This presentation will outline the communication strategy related to a recent DSpace 7 upgrade for a large repository (more than 100,000 items). The presenter will share the communication plan related to the software upgrade, some of the tools that are used to keep track of communication with individual collections and users, and feedback from user surveys related to library support of the repository.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 309 / 24X702: 5 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Overlay Services ; COAR Notify ; Linked Data Notifications ; preprints ; Next generation repositories</p> <p>Promoting the use of preprints and overlay services on the HAL open archive with COAR Notify Raphaël Tournay CCSD/CNRS, France</p> <p>HAL is a multidisciplinary open archive for the dissemination of scientific knowledge. It is part of the French Ministry's roadmap for research infrastructures and the National Plan for Open Science.</p> <p>Episciences overlay journals and Peer Community In (PCI) are two types of overlay services offering peer review of preprints and operating on top of several preprint servers. A common challenge with this type of service is the lack of standards for interoperability with open repositories.</p> <p>This problem of interoperability is solved by the COAR Notify initiative proposed by COAR. HAL, Episciences and PCI are among the first to have adopted this initiative, making effective use of several use cases supported by the recommendations. This presentation will explain how we have used COAR Notify to implement easier workflows for researchers and how it is helping to promote the submission of preprints to HAL. The new services also offer greater visibility and encourage the use of overlay services such as Episciences and PCI.</p> <p>We hope that this presentation will generate interest in the adoption of COAR Notify among managers of open-repositories and pre-publication servers. One of HAL's ambitions for the future is to be able to offer more overlay services to researchers.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 337 / 24X702: 6 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Fediverse, COAR-Notify, ActivityPub, distributed</p> <p>Should repositories participate in the Fediverse? Paul Walk Antleaf Ltd.</p> <p>This lightning talk will present the argument that our distributed network of repositories has much in common - both in terms of intent and in terms of technology - with the emerging "Fediverse" of social-network services. The Fediverse represents an opportunity for repositories to radically increase user-engagement, by easily and seamlessly linking them with the new generation of social-media platforms. The talk will argue that repositories have an opportunity to engage with the Fediverse, to help usher in a new paradigm of more user-centric scholarly communication.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 211 / 24X702: 7 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> African Data, Repository, Knowledge sharing, Preservation`1</p> <p>Opening the Hidden Treasure of African data and information towards community representation: The National Repository of Nigeria (NRN) Engagement Chinwe Veronica Anunobi, Chukwuemeka Kelvin Udoji National Library of Nigeria, Nigeria</p> <p>Global insinuation is the near absence of African data and information for knowledge sharing. This cannot be understood to mean lack of documented evidence but their unavailability for global access and use. Though Africa, particularly Nigerian scholars are at cutting edge of research endeavours and very prolific, only few resources published in international outlets are available for use globally. The result is a misconception and biases in assessment and inferences concerning Africa. However, many traditional print repositories have data of rich African heritage outside the reach of the global communities. Consequently, efforts were put in place in Nigeria to open up her greatest rich heritage as preserved in the National library of Nigeria. The Library engaged in the implementation of the National Repository of Nigeria (NRN) as an effort to have Nigerian data represented globally. The Repository which aim is to bridge the gap in the underrepresentation of Nigeria's rich cultural heritage was deployed in 2022. The paper intends to present efforts of the Library to open up over five million cultural heritage of Nigeria which were deposited since its establishment. Some of the success stories and challenges especially in the areas of competencies and technology will be discuss.</p>
<p>09:00 - 10:30</p>	<p>Developer Track Session 2 Location: Drottningporten 2 Session Chair: Kathryn Cassidy, Trinity College Dublin</p>
	<p>ID: 108 / DV02: 1 Developer Track <i>Topics:</i> Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Software Development, Technical Debt, Student Experiential Learning, Research Datasets</p> <p>Experiential Learning and Technical Debt Clinton Graham University of Pittsburgh, United States of America</p> <p>Experimental student projects provide a low-barrier opportunity for research universities to both support student learning and to pilot novel presentations of institutional research and data. This is particularly advantageous when students of a minority community are enabled to tell the stories of the research data of that minority community. The unresolved risk, however, is the ongoing stewardship of this work, as such an experimental or pilot project represents an inherited technical debt after the students have graduated.</p>

This presentation will describe one such student endeavor as a case study. At the University of Pittsburgh, the University Library System and the School of Computing and Information Science partnered to create a query/visualization tool highlighting a distinctive-collections deposit within the University's institutional repository of transcriptions of a substantial Chinese village gazetteer collection. The presenter will reflect on successes and challenges of this project and will invite conversation on similar technical management of experimental/pilot student projects which highlight institutional repositories' research and datasets.

ID: 264 / DV02: 2

Developer Track

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Research Object Crate (RO-Crate), Linked data metadata

Crate-O - a drop-in linked data metadata editor for RO-Crate (and other) linked data in repositories and beyond

Peter Sefton, Alvin Sebastian, Moises Sacal Bonequi, Rosanna Smith

University of Queensland, Australia

Research Object Crate is a metadata packaging standard which has been widely adopted over the last few years in research contexts and which debuted at Open Repositories with a workshop in 2019.

In this presentation we will show a new tool, Crate-O, that implements the specification, allowing data to be described at multiple scales.

Crate-O is a browser-based tool which can work in a wide variety of environments – as an online metadata editor, for describing local data on a user's hard disk, and as a way of describing entire collections of data, whether legacy or contemporary, either with an easy-to-use GUI or in bulk via spreadsheets.

ID: 276 / DV02: 3

Developer Track

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems

Keywords: BinderHub, Interactive Computing, Reproducible Research, CKAN

Bringing computation and reproducibility to a data repository using Binder

Cheng-Jen Lee, Tyng-Ruey Chuang

Academia Sinica, Taiwan

The Binder is an online service that allows users to create and share executable computing environments from datasets in data repositories such as GitHub, Zenodo, or Dataverse. In this talk, we will share our experiences about how to customize and deploy a Binder service at the depositor, a research data repository built on top of CKAN.

ID: 384 / DV02: 4

Developer Track

Topics: Research Transparency, Climate Justice, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Reproducible Science, Big Data, Fedora Repository, Knowledge Graphs, Open Repositories

Translating Large Datasets for Reproducible Science in an Open Repository

Jake Alan Rosenberg, Vanessa Gonzalez, Sarah Gray, Maria Esteve

Texas Advanced Computing Center, United States of America

The DesignSafe cyberinfrastructure provides comprehensive support for the entire natural hazards research data life cycle. As a science gateway, it equips researchers with tools to manage large datasets and analyze them using high-performance computing (HPC) resources, then curate and publish the results. The CoreTrustSeal-certified Data Depot Repository (DDR) uniquely addresses HPC and archival needs through a knowledge graph-based data curation architecture. Natural hazards research methods are modeled as categories and metadata, guiding researchers to create consistent and complete datasets with clear technical and administrative provenance. The repository architecture supports reuse within the HPC ecosystem by standardizing the formats of large datasets, enhancing their discoverability. DesignSafe employs NetworkX for constructing and manipulating knowledge graphs, ensuring their preservation through mappings to directory structures in replicated storage, alongside container hierarchies in the Fedora repository software. This developer-focused presentation delves into the architecture and implementation details of DesignSafe's knowledge graph repository. The content will be relevant to developers and repository administrators interested in using open repositories to support high-performance computing and reproducible science.

ID: 110 / DV02: 5

Developer Track

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems

Keywords: Indigenous languages, archives, OCFL, open source

Using Fedora 6 to architect future-proof and easily maintained repositories

Dustin Slater

University of Texas at Austin, United States of America

At the University of Texas at Austin Libraries we have several Digital Asset Management Systems (DAMS) performing a variety of functions, most of which were in Islandora 7. With the Drupal 7 end of life we pursued rebuilding each of these platforms, which was complicated and labor-intensive. We sought to find another approach to solving this problem, one which would allow us to both modularize the infrastructure to move away from a monolithic implementation and adopt the Oxford Common File Layout (OCFL) as our storage layer to prevent needing future data migrations. Fedora 6 allowed us to rethink how to solve our DAMS challenges by providing OCFL and an API to access the data. With this as our foundation, we embarked on rebuilding our Archive of the Indigenous Languages of Latin America portal using a selection of open-source technologies. This resulted in a trilingual portal that is attractive, flexible, and sustainable. We are excited to have completed this project during the International Decade of Indigenous Languages and look forward to seeing how communities all over the world will continue to use the content to reclaim their languages.

ID: 347 / DV02: 6

Developer Track

Topics: Repository Systems

Keywords: application repository, data science app sharing, machine learning model sharing

Building a repository of data science and machine learning applications by leveraging on container images and Kubernetes

Arnold Kochari

SciLifeLab, Uppsala University, Uppsala, Sweden

An increasing number of research projects produces machine learning models and data science applications a need arises for long-term hosting of these research outputs. To meet this need, we built a custom repository focused specifically on sharing machine learning models and data science applications (SciLifeLab Serve, <https://serve.scilifelab.se>); it is currently available to life science researchers affiliated with Swedish research institutions. Our repository is essentially a hosting platform where the submitted models and data science applications become available for inferences over an API endpoint or for interactions through a graphical web interface. We built a dedicated user interface (Django application) on top of a Kubernetes cluster (using Kubernetes API to control deployments). Each submission to our repository is a Docker image or is turned into a Docker image based on user input; this image is then running in the Kubernetes cluster. This approach allows for easy scalability, efficiency of resource utilization, quick deployment and updates.

In this presentation we will demonstrate the service, talk about interesting features, our tech stack as well as some of the challenges and our solutions so far. The code behind the platform that we developed is open source allowing anyone to launch an instance of it.

09:00 - 10:30

Presentations: Transparency and Reproducibility

Location: **Drottningporten 3**

Session Chair: **Nora Mulvaney**, Toronto Metropolitan University

ID: 159 / PR07: 1

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability
Keywords: disciplinary repository; quality assurance; transparency

Quality Assurance in Service of Transparency: A Practice Report from PsychArchives, the Disciplinary Repository for Psychology

Yi-Hsiu Chen, Marie-Luise Müller, Lea Gerhards, Anne Königs, Peter Weiland, Christiane Baier, Martin Kock, Hannah Franke
Leibniz Institute for Psychology (ZPID), Germany

PsychArchives is a disciplinary repository for psychological science and neighboring disciplines. To ensure the quality of all submissions, PsychArchives implements a comprehensive set of quality assurance measures, containing both manual and automated processes.

Individual researchers can submit their content via a customized submission platform. To populate the repository with content, PsychArchives also cooperates with publishers, conference organizers, and other institutions. A consequence of these two varying ways of ingesting content – individual submission and batch import – is the implementation of two different quality assurance workflows, which nevertheless share the same goal.

This paper will outline how quality is defined when it comes to PsychArchives DROs, and will demonstrate a number of ways in which quality is assured during and after the submission of content to the repository. While this paper aims to present solutions and lessons learned in practice, we also want to highlight some challenges we are still facing regarding the quality management of PsychArchives content. By providing insight into the internal quality workflows of PsychArchives, we aim to shed light on how quality assurance is an essential prerequisite for transparency and reusability of research-related output archived in a disciplinary repository.

ID: 305 / PR07: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability
Keywords: Publication Cost, Transparency, Metadata Schema

The OpenCost project - Using repositories to achieve transparency in the transformation process to open access as part of the science economy

Julia Bartlewski¹, Christoph Broschinski¹, Gernot Deinzer², Dirk Pieper¹, Bianca Schweighofer², Colin Sippl², Lisa-Marie Stein³, Alexander Wagner³, Silke Weisheit²

¹University of Bielefeld, Germany; ²University of Regensburg, Germany; ³DESY, Germany

The "openCost" project introduces a standardized metadata schema developed in collaboration with libraries and international experts on publication costs. The schema contains metadata on payments and contracts related to publication, enabling the identification of hidden costs and providing a detailed breakdown of publication costs. The use of well-connected interfaces such as OAI-PMH enables efficient data exchange and harvesting by service providers. This approach not only increases the transparency of publication costs, but also promotes cross-institutional comparisons at national and international level, benefiting both the institutions involved and the funders.

ID: 353 / PR07: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability
Keywords: CRIS, RIMS, OMEGA-PSIR, RESEARCH TRANSPARENCY

University Research Management and Open Science - an OMEGA-PSIR case study

Łukasz Skonieczny, Henryk Rybiński, Jakub Koperwas

Warsaw University of Technology, Poland

This workshop aims to demonstrate how integrating various functionalities into a single system can transform university management and enhance open science promotion and research support. Targeting university administrators, research managers, and academic staff, the workshop focuses on the strategic and practical aspects of implementing an integrated system like OMEGA-PSIR, exemplified by the experience at Warsaw University of Technology.

The workshop will cover a range of topics, including a brief introduction to the integrated system's functions, emphasizing its role as a semantic knowledge base where everything is interconnected. It will delve into the system's basics in the context of university research data management and assess the impact of data integration on open science initiatives and university operations.

Key areas of discussion include techniques for boosting global visibility of university research, enhancing internal processes for project collaborations and partner selection, and optimizing research management and reporting through OMEGA-PSIR. The workshop will also explore efficient resource allocation strategies, including identifying top teams, successful international collaborations, and promising young academic talents, and strategies for fair distribution of research resources.

09:00 - 10:30

Presentations: Supporting Climate and Environmental Data

Location: Brevsorterarsalen 1

Session Chair: Camilla Lindelow, University of Borås

ID: 231 / PR08: 1

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Brazilian scientific ecosystem, BrCris, Current Research Information Systems, Research Data Repository

Preservation of data from the Brazilian scientific ecosystem: Periodic ingestion of data originating from Br-Cris into the Aleia Research Data Repository

Laura Vilela Rodrigues Rezende¹, Marcel Souza², Priscila Sena³, Washington Segundo²

¹Universidade Federal de Goiás, Brazil; ²Instituto Brasileiro de Informação em Ciência e Tecnologia; ³Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul

In the context of opening up scientific data, standards, principles and recommendations, the development of CRIS Current Research Information System) around the world makes these information increasingly intelligible and useful, as long as they have been previously prepared. In Brazilian context, the BrCRIS, developed and launched in 2023 by Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology, establishes a unique scientific information organizational model of the entire Brazilian research ecosystem. In research institutions, analyzing this range of information is strategically important to develop key indicators and outline scenarios for decision-making. This study presents a proposal of implementation of periodic ingestion of BrCris datasets into Aleia Repository, from Ibit, aiming to provide time frames of raw data relating to the Brazilian scientific ecosystem as data to support scientific and governor spheres, among the entire society.

ID: 338 / PR08: 2

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability
Keywords: AGRIS, Zero Hunger, Agricultural Global Knowledge, Multilingualism, Discoverability

AGRS Multilinguality in Bridging Agricultural Knowledge Gaps for Zero Hunger

Alicia Garcia Garcia¹, Valentina De Col², Stefano Anibaldi², José Antonio Hernandez¹, Tiziano Di Condina¹, Jaime García Llopis¹, Tiziano Lorenzetti¹, Ruth Velia Gómez¹, Imma Subirats Coll¹, Jaime García Llopis¹

¹Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO); ²International Center for Agricultural Research in Dry Areas (ICARDA)

In defeating hunger and realizing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) acknowledges that knowledge is pivotal and must be shared globally. To empower global progress, the visibility and discoverability of multilingual resources beyond English become critical. FAO's International System for Agricultural Science and Technology (AGRIS) catalyzes this global advancement. The AGRIS network comprises the AGRIS database of over 13.8 million bibliographic records in 90+ languages (as of January 2024) and a collaborative network of data providers from more than 150 countries worldwide, contributing to the richness and content diversity of the AGRIS database. Multilingualism through the use of different metadata schemas, standardized language codes, and use of the FAO's AGROVOC multilingual thesaurus allows the content in AGRIS to be discoverable by different stakeholders, facilitating the knowledge sharing needed to foster global efforts to combat hunger.

ID: 371 / PR08: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Climate Justice, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Climate Change and Health, Research Coordinating Center, Harvard Dataverse Repository

CAFÉ: A Joint BUSPH-HSPH Research Coordinating Center of the NIH Climate Change and Health Initiative Leveraging Harvard Dataverse Repository

Sonia Barbosa¹, Stefano Aicus¹, Joshua S. Cetron², Kezia Irene², Michelle Audirac², Gregory A. Wellenius³, Amruta Nori-Sarma³, Francesca Dominici², Kevin Lane³, Danielle Braun²

¹IQSS, Harvard University; ²Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health; ³Boston University School of Public Health

Climate change health (CCH) research is currently hampered by (1) a fractured community of practice (COP) that is frequently siloed by discipline and concentrated in well-resourced institutions and countries; (2) innovative data assets that exist but are often hard to find, inconsistently documented, and challenging to manage and link to other data resources; (3) lack of access, especially by early-stage investigators, to necessary data and computing environments; and (4) lack of a centralized platform to support the domestic and global capacity-building initiatives needed to expand the COP. To address these challenges we recently launched the BUSPH-HSPH-CAFÉ (the CAFÉ), the joint BUSPH-HSPH Research Coordinating Center (RCC) of the NIH Climate Change and Health Initiative that leverages the state-of-the-art CCH research, education, and policy translation ecosystem of Boston University School of Public Health and Harvard University. The CAFÉ includes a data management function, which is establishing a centralized framework for disseminating data, with complete and standardized metadata and documentation in compliance with the Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR) principles for data sharing. Our approach leverages the Harvard Dataverse Repository, an established and rapidly growing NIH-supported and -funded research data repository (project number 10T2DB00004-01), in conjunction with GitHub and other state-of-the-art tools.

ID: 208 / PR08: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Climate Justice, Repository Systems

Keywords: Research, Transparency, Sustainability, Community

Appalachian Research and Value for the Greater Good

Robin Ruggaber

University of Virginia Library, United States of America

The University of Virginia at Wise (UVA Wise) is located on 396 acres in central Appalachia, rich in mixed land use, and biodiversity. The Appalachian economy continues to struggle due to the environmental impact of coal mining, the decline of the coal industry, the opioid crisis, the coronavirus pandemic, and now climate change. UVA Wise conducts valuable research pertinent to the problems facing the region and underrepresented communities but has no repository infrastructure or scholarly communication services. In the fall of 2023, librarians, and researchers of the University of Virginia (UVA) and UVA Wise began collaborating to preserve and provide public access to UVA Wise's federally funded research by leveraging UVA's repository infrastructure. A second phase involves building a UVA Wise research portal to showcase the research, its value, and scholarly communication services, providing library resources (employing students, funding digitization equipment), hosting a research showcase event, conducting student research advocacy, and assessing data to measure impact. The presentation will focus on the problems facing the region, specific UVA Wise research relating to those problems, explore the value of this research to disproportionately impacted communities, and explore the value of elevating the visibility of research at the smaller institution.

09:00 - 10:30

Panel: Rights Retention and Repositories

Location: **Brevsorterarsalen 2**

Session Chair: **Torsten Reimer**, University of Chicago

ID: 359 / PAN04: 1

Panels

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems

Keywords: Rights Retention

Rights Retention and Repositories: Accelerating Global Progress

William J. Nixon¹, Dominic Tate⁴, Kathleen Shearer², Sally Rumsey³, George Macgregor⁵

¹Research Libraries UK (RLUK), United Kingdom; ²Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR); ³COALition S; ⁴University of Edinburgh; ⁵University of Glasgow

In the last couple of years in the UK there's been a not so quiet revolution in the adoption of institutional Rights Retention Policies (IRRP) which has been gathering momentum. There are now 26 institutions with IRPs now in place, with more planned.

While Rights Retention is not new, it was pioneered in 2008 at Harvard, in the UK however, 2023 felt like a tipping point with statements and policies released at institutional, regional and national levels.

The Rights Retention revolution is here. Authors rights are at the heart of the scholarly dissemination process. With the support, and leadership of research libraries we can ensure academia's control of original copyrights becomes the new norm, enabling and protecting free and open access to research for the public good. How can our institutional repositories be best placed to support this new norm?

The panel will explore the role that Institutional repositories (and their supporting infrastructure and services) can play in supporting Rights Retention, and in turn empowering authors and accelerating global scholarship.

09:00 - 10:30

Presentations: Author Identifiers and Information

Location: **Brevsorterarsalen 3**

Session Chair: **Jessica Lindholm**, Chalmers University of Technology

ID: 323 / PR23: 1

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems

Keywords: ORCID, DSpace, DSpace-CRIS

Understanding and using the ORCID integration in DSpace and DSpace-CRIS

Oliver Goldschmidt

TU Hamburg, Germany

PIDs like ORCID or DOI can be considered as the probably most important pillars to empower global progress to repository systems. Today any repository software should have a working ORCID integration to help the users to distinguish persons on a global level and another persistent identifier to address publications.

The well-known repository software DSpace has a working integration of ORCID, which has been introduced in DSpace 7.3 (June 2022). But even in the currently latest version DSpace 7.6 it's still not complete.

DSpace-CRIS is a software, which is very much tied to DSpace, but it's a standalone software. It is developed by 4Science and is containing a complete ORCID integration for a long time.

Hamburg University of Technology recently conducted a project in cooperation with 4Science, which was funded by ORCID in context of the Global Participation Fund. The project's goal was to improve the login process against ORCID for DSpace-CRIS.

This presentation will focus on the project results, but it will also show, how the ORCID integration in DSpace-CRIS and DSpace can be used at all. It will also explain the differences of the integration levels between DSpace and DSpace-CRIS and compare the two platforms regarding their ORCID integration.

ID: 361 / PR23: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency

Keywords: PIDs, trust, transparency, integrity, interoperability

Strengthening the Global Community Trust Network: Empowering Transparency in Scholarly Infrastructure through ORCID Integration

Lombe Tembo

ORCID, Zambia

Building a transparent Global Community Trust Network is imperative for fostering a robust and trustworthy environment for scholarly information systems worldwide. This proposal advocates for the importance of enriching ORCID records with trustworthy data as an essential step in achieving this overarching goal. By contributing to a network that encompasses the global research ecosystem, our collective efforts can significantly enhance the integrity, transparency, and accessibility of scholarly information.

ID: 271 / PR23: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Interoperability; Contributor Identifiers; Distributed Web; Next Generation Repositories

authorIDy: Listing Contributions by Contributor Identifier

Patrick Hochstenbach², Herbert Van de Sompel¹, Martin Klein³, Ingrid Dillo¹

¹DANS, Netherlands; ²Ghent University, Belgium; ³Los Alamos National Laboratory, USA

Increasingly, repositories allow, recommend, or require providing unique contributor identifiers, such as ORCID or ISNI, when depositing contributions. Despite this evolution, few repositories provide a machine interface that allows listing the contributions made by a researcher using their contributor identifier as a key. An interface with this capability, supported across repositories, would facilitate a range of use cases and could be an important next step towards realizing COAR's Next Generation Repositories vision. This presentation will introduce the core characteristics of authorIDy, a conceptual proposal for such a machine interface. The presentation is mainly aimed at soliciting feedback to inform next steps. Therefor, sufficiently in advance of the presentation, a document will be made available that gives an overview of key aspects of the proposal, which has simplicity at its core.

ID: 313 / PR23: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Rights-retention, RSS, machine learning

Identifying and extracting authors' Rights Retention Statements from full text academic articles

Matteo Cancellieri, Anton Zhuk, Valerii Budko, Ekaterine Chxaidze, Viktoriia Pavlenko, Petr Knoth

Open University, United Kingdom

Many research performing institutes are adopting Rights Retention strategies to help their authors maintain copyright ownership of their work, whilst also enabling broader access and compliance with funder mandates such as Plan S. The implementation of a Rights Retention Strategy offers numerous advantages, including open access assurance, copyright retention, scholarly use regulation, enhanced dissemination, equity promotion, and facilitation of text and data mining. However, the manual incorporation of appropriate rights retention statements into article metadata is labour-intensive and time-consuming.

To address this challenge, CORE has co-designed, with repository managers, a machine learning module to automatically identify and extract rights retention statements from full-text articles, streamlining the encoding of this information within article metadata. The integration of CORE services with repository software and the expansion of data extraction capabilities are crucial steps toward promoting a more accessible, transparent and interconnected scholarly ecosystem.

10:30 - 11:00

Coffee Break

11:00 - 12:30

Presentations: Integrations for Research Data Management

Location: **Drottningporten 1**

Session Chair: **Katie Mika**, Harvard University

ID: 285 / PR09: 1

Presentations

Topics: Responsible Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: reproducibility, open science, repositories, software assets

Making Software FAIR: A machine-assisted workflow for the research software lifecycle

Petr Knoth¹, Laurent Romary², Patrice Lopez³, Roberto Di Cosmo², Pavel Smrz⁴, Tomasz Umerle⁵, Melissa Harrison⁶, Alain Monteil², Matteo Cancellieri¹, David Pride¹

¹CORE, The Open University, United Kingdom; ²Inria; ³Science Miner; ⁴Brno University of Technology; ⁵Polish Academy of Sciences;

⁶European Institute of Bioinformatics

A key issue hindering discoverability, attribution and reusability of open research software is that its existence often remains hidden within the manuscript of research papers. For these resources to become first-class bibliographic records, they first need to be identified and subsequently registered with persistent identifiers (PIDs) to be made FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). To this day, much open research software fails to meet FAIR principles and software resources are mostly not explicitly linked from the manuscripts that introduced them or used them.

SoFAIR is a 2-year international project (2024-2025) which proposes a solution to the above problem realised over the content available through the global network of open repositories. SoFAIR will extend the capabilities of widely used open scholarly infrastructures (CORE, Software Heritage, HAL) and tools (GROBID) operated by the consortium partners, delivering and deploying an effective solution for the management of the research software lifecycle, including: 1) ML-assisted identification of research software assets from within the manuscripts of scholarly papers, 2) validation of the identified assets by authors, 3) registration of software assets with PIDs and their archival.

ID: 295 / PR09: 2

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Repository benchmarks, performance testing, research data, scalability

Real-World Benchmarks for FAIR Data Repositories: Meeting the Needs for Modern Open Data

Arran Griffith¹, Maria Esteve², Dan Field¹

¹Fedora; ²Texas Advanced Computing Center, University of Texas at Austin

Data repositories are fundamental infrastructure in the open science ecosystem, however traditional repository systems now face the challenge of keeping pace with the ever-growing and exponentially increasing scale of modern research data production. Currently, there is limited understanding of how an implementation involving Fedora 6.x in a High Performance Computing (HPC) environment may influence data scalability and functional efficiency of the repository.

This presentation will provide an in-depth look on on-going collaboration between the Fedora program team and data intensive computing and cloud developers at Texas Advanced Computing Center (TACC), to address the performance and scalability limits of Fedora 6.x in a high-performance computing (HPC) environment. Results of this collaboration will provide both the Fedora users and the repository community at large, with a better understanding of the scalability of a repository environment and how to assess it systematically. These crucial performance metrics will allow data repository technical, curatorial and administrative staff to understand how to optimize their infrastructure to meet the demand for management and access of large open data.

ID: 332 / PR09: 3

Presentations

Topics: Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: linked data, FAIR data, repository comparison, standardisation

Resolving Linked Data: Are we all doing the same?

Mateusz Żółtak, Martina Trognitz

Austrian Academy of Sciences, Austria

Linked Data is a standard widely used to help in providing FAIR data and metadata. We present a more in detail analysis on what the requirements for Linked Data are and how they are technically implemented in various repositories and authority services. The comparison focusing on the usability of the responses provided by the services resolving a requested URI shows notable differences. The results call for a formulation of an updated set of Linked Data principles to enhance (meta)data findability, accessibility and interoperability.

ID: 262 / PR09: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Metadata Standards; RO-Crate; Repository Tools; Open Source; Linked Data; FAIR Principles

Five ways RO-Crate data packages are important for repositories

Peter Sefton¹, Stian Soiland-Reyes²

¹University of Queensland, Australia; ²The University of Manchester, UK

Research Object Crate is a linked data metadata packaging standard which has been widely adopted in research contexts. In this presentation we will briefly explain what RO-Crate is, how it is being adopted worldwide, then go on to list ways that RO-Crate is growing in importance in the repository world:

- Uploading of complex multi-file objects means RO-Crate is compatible with any general purpose repository that can accept a zip file (with some coding, repository services can do more with RO-Crates)
- Download for well-described data objects complete with metadata from a repository rather than just a zip or file with no metadata
- Using RO-Crate metadata reduces the amount of customisation that is required in repository software, as ALL the metadata is described using the same simple, self-documenting linked-data structures, so generic display templates
- Sufficiently well-described RO-Crates can be used to make data FAIR compliant, aiding in Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability thanks to standardised metadata and mature tooling
- And if you're looking for a sustainable repository solution, there are tools which can run a repository from a set of static files on a storage service, in line with the ideas put forward by Suleman in the closing keynote for OR2023

11:00 - 12:30

Presentations: CRIS and Other System Integrations

Location: **Drottningporten 2**

Session Chair: **Kristin Olofsson**, Chalmers University of Technology

ID: 333 / PR10: 1

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: COAR Notify, Repository Integrations

A Repository-to-Repository Implementation of COAR Notify: Enabling Informed and Comprehensive Research Integration

William Fyson, Rory McNicholl

CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom

The COAR Notify protocol offers an enhanced approach for allowing repositories to communicate with not just other services and platforms but also related repositories. This proposal examines how two or more EPrints repositories within a same institution interact at present, the flaws with the approach used and how COAR Notify can offer an improved workflow. Two potential use cases for the COAR Notify protocol are proposed with a demonstration of how this improves upon current implementations by more closely involving depositors and repository editors in the process. This in turn helps to ensure that content across different, but related repository platforms is kept up to date, correct and complete, and enables new workflows for managing research outputs, as well as the potential for future integrations with a wide array of platforms and services through a standardized and open protocol.

ID: 349 / PR10: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Open Science, Scientific Information Systems, Data Integration, Scientific Production

Integration of Open Access Repositories in BrCris: Aiming to Understand the Brazilian Scientific Research Ecosystem

Marcel Souza¹, Washington Luís Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo¹, Thiago Magela Rodrigues Dias², Patricia da Silva Neubert³, Fábio Lorensi do Canto³

¹Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Brazil; ²Centro Federal de Educação Tecnológica de Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), Brazil; ³Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina (UFSC), Brasil

In recent years, several initiatives aimed at creating systems that manage the academic production of an institution, country or area of knowledge have received attention from different areas. Such systems are known by the acronym CRIS (Current Research Information Systems) and are intended to aggregate information from various databases in order to provide reports, consolidated data for researchers to analyze, as well as being the object of certification of scientific information and technological. Therefore, this work presents the data integration process of the BrCris Platform with the objective of providing reliable data, so that it is possible to carry out the information certification process about the Brazilian scientific community. This strategy presents itself as an important data aggregation mechanism, providing reliable and important information about scientific data, especially about Brazilian scientific and technological production. Therefore, the use of aggregated data from the BrCris Platform for the process of understanding the ecosystem of Brazilian scientific research will provide several bibliometric studies that would a priori be extremely complex in their preparation.

ID: 189 / PR10: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems

Keywords: Scholarly Communication, Decentralized Web, Open Science.

Using an Event Notification Network for Transparent Sharing of Artifact Life Cycle Data

Patrick Hochstenbach¹, Ruben Verborgh¹, Herbert Van de Sompele^{1,2}

¹Ghent University, Belgium; ²Data Archiving and Networked Services

Scholars rely on a vast network of databases containing peer and non-peer reviewed artifacts to conduct their research. In their quest for information, filtering out what to read or not, they rely on heuristics to access the trustworthiness of the artifacts. Life-cycle information could be used to create better assessments, but this information is spread over many networks, hidden in web pages, or not made available at all. We propose a decentralized communication system in which nodes in a network use a messaging protocol to inform each other about important life-cycle events. This presentation introduces the Event Notifications messaging protocol to orchestrate life-cycle events or exchange information about them. We present how this protocol is implemented in the COAR Notify project connecting institutional repositories with peer-review and overlay journal services. The protocol does not only provide interoperable layer for life-cycle event, but it also provides the technology for a decentralized scholarly communication system in line with COAR's Next Generation Repository report. In a next phase of Event Notifications, a persistent layer of life-cycle information in the form of Event Logs will be investigated. Using Event Notifications and Event Logs a transparent, interoperable sharing of linkages between research outputs can be achieved.

11:00 - 12:30

Presentations: Using Repositories for Diverse Content Types

Location: **Drottningporten 3**

Session Chair: **Ilkay Holt**, British Library

ID: 317 / PR11: 1

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: Open Science ; Open repositories ; Innovation process ; Patents ; Cooperation

Open Repositories Contributors to Open Innovation Strategies: Sharing Data and Knowledge on Patents

Ricardo EITO BRUN

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain

Innovation management is a sub-discipline of management that studies the rules that govern the generation, diffusion and adoption of innovation, and the relationships between innovation inputs and outputs. Innovation management was traditionally understood as a linear model that comprised a sequence of activities – from basic research to serial production and market launch -, completed by a single entity. In the linear model, the achievement of innovations was determined by the planning, financing and execution of internal R&D activities or external technology acquisition.

Linear models were replaced by collaborative models based on feedback and interactions between different partners (Busse, 2013; Harmelen 2012). Today, innovation management is seen as a non-linear, evolutionary, interactive process between the company and its environment that requires the close collaboration of different agents (Iordatiu, 2013). This evolution culminated in the Open Innovation Model.

Open Innovation is based on the open cooperation and sharing of information and knowledge. This presentation describes how open repositories can contribute to share and promote open innovation activities based on a practical proposal to create knowledge sharing communities around document repositories, with an emphasis on patents.

ID: 204 / PR11: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems

Keywords: TRIZ, Wikipedia, effects database

Towards an open TRIZ multilingual database

Dênis Leonardo Zaniro^{1,2,3}, Luc Quoniam^{1,3}, Marcel Garcia de Souza³, Washington Luís Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo³

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Background: TRIZ (Russian acronym for the Theory of Inventive Problem Solving) is an innovation methodology widely accepted in various countries. To facilitate the practical application of this methodology in problem-solving, scientific, and engineering effects databases have been developed in recent years. Problem: In this context, it was found that databases adhering to the principle of freedom of information are predominantly unilingual, restricting access to specific groups based on their language, culture, and socio-economic situation. Additionally, there is no standardization in the structure of these databases, and usability and coverage aspects are not fully met by any analyzed database. Approach: To address the identified gaps, two databases maintained by different consulting institutions were selected. After extracting and organizing the data, an integration process was conducted to identify redundancies and expand solution models into a single open repository. To become multilingual, the unified TRIZ database was integrated with Wikipedias in different languages. The database construction process was automated through algorithm implementation. Conclusions: According to the achieved result and initial assessments by experts in technological information, the TRIZ multilingual database represents the first step towards democratizing access to the TRIZ methodology, in line with frugal innovation and open science.

ID: 335 / PR11: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities

Keywords: open access, monographs, institutional repositories, archiving and preservation

Thoth Archiving Network: How institutional repositories can become involved in preserving long-form scholarship

Miranda L Barnes

Loughborough University, United Kingdom

The Thoth Archiving Network (TAN), developed within the COPIM Project and continuing as part of Open Book Futures (a Copim community project), is a network of participating University repositories and web-archiving platforms working to archive digital open access monographs from small and scholar-led publishers. TAN operates as part of Thoth, an open metadata management and dissemination platform and service, also created as part of COPIM. The aim of the Thoth Archiving Network is to allow for the small and scholar-led press, as well as other small to medium independent presses, an accessible way to quickly and easily deposit their OA monographs into participating institutional repositories and web-archiving platforms in an 'archiving as dissemination' workflow, to prevent against loss and ensure continuing access. TAN is an opportunity for institutional repositories and higher education institutions to contribute tangibly towards the advancement of the open access ecosystem, in addition to progressive financial contributions already being made by some universities towards OA initiatives and infrastructure.

11:00 - 12:30

Panel: DSpace

Location: **Brevsorterarsalen 2**

Session Chair: **Nora Mulvaney**, Toronto Metropolitan University

ID: 140 / PAN05: 1

Panels

Topics: Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: DSpace, roadmap, community, collaboration

DSpace 8.0 and Beyond: What's new and how a global community makes DSpace happen

Tim Donohue¹, Michele Mennielli¹, Susanna Mornati², Ignace Deroost³, Agustina Martínez-García⁴, Kristi Park⁵, Andrea Bollini²

¹Lyrasis, United States; ²4Science, Italy; ³Atmire, Belgium; ⁴University of Cambridge, United Kingdom; ⁵Texas Digital Library, United States

This panel session will provide an update on all DSpace activities from the institutions most involved in the latest release, DSpace 8.0. DSpace 8.0 is scheduled to be released in April 2024 and follows in the footsteps of the transformative 7.x series of releases. This release prioritizes new features which empower your administrators, including a new data correction/notification service which allows DSpace to be notified of potential data quality improvements to existing research objects in the system.

The panel will include demonstrations of DSpace 8 features from some of the institutions which built them. It will also provide updates from the DSpace Steering Group on the upcoming roadmap, including priorities for version 9.0 (due in April 2025) and maintenance of 7.x and 8.x. Finally, this panel will discuss current and planned DSpace community activities, along with ways that institutions can get involved or support DSpace by becoming a member or contributor.

11:00 - 12:30

Presentations: Data Repositories and Lessons Learned

Location: **Brevsorterarsalen 3**

Session Chair: **Elizabeth Krzrnarich**, DataCite

ID: 373 / PR22: 1

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Shared infrastructure, multi-tenant repositories, open science infrastructure, national repository strategy, community of practice

Shared repositories infrastructure: Extracting Global Gains from a Strategic National Approach

Susan Haigh¹, Geoff Harder², Kathleen Shearer³, Kate Davis⁴, Lee Wilson⁵

¹Canadian Association of Research Libraries; ²University of Alberta; ³COAR; ⁴Scholars Portal; ⁵Digital Research Alliance of Canada

In an era marked by the accelerating pace of scholarly communication and data-driven research, Canadian libraries are spearheading collaborative scholarly communications infrastructure at the national level to support shared repositories and related services. This session aims to present an overview of the concerted efforts across Canadian institutions to enhance the accessibility and interoperability of institutional repository content, research data, and more.

The presentation will delve into the landscape of service development, with a focus on the coordination of infrastructure components such as Persistent Identifiers (PIDs), the Federated Research Data Repository (FRDR), the Borealis Dataverse service, and the most recent development of a shared national institutional repository service. Concrete examples and case studies will highlight the successful implementation of these services, offering valuable insights into the challenges faced, solutions devised, and lessons learned.

The significance of this collaboration extends beyond borders; the Canadian experience helps support a larger blueprint for global progress in scholarly communication and open science. By fostering dialogue on lessons learned through community building, and unveiling future roadmaps, the session underscores the key role played by our networks - operating at scale and investing in collaborative efforts to empower the international research community.

ID: 368 / PR22: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Research data, Data migration, Open Source, Software development, Repository management

Agility, Growth, and Cooperative Service Design: two teams building a data repository during times of change

Katherine Lynch, Meghan Testerman

Princeton University, United States of America

In 2024, Princeton University launched new data repository services with the Princeton Data Commons. It spanned many challenges, including departmental restructures, new staff, and support for an existing critical service in brittle legacy architecture while developing a better way to support research data.

Rather than replacing one monolithic system with another, we reimagined a decoupled ecosystem of softwares serving the needs of researchers at each stage of their work, from ingestion through publication. Taking advantage of the best tools for research data management such as description using DataCite and managing permanent identifiers with DOIs, it gave us the opportunity to revisit data previously stored in a system not designed for it, and to create better repository objects in a hands-on review process. However, this project also represented a shift in user workflows established for nearly a decade, and presented new work in terms of non-automated data migration from the legacy system to the new one, a worthwhile challenge but one not often taken on in projects such as this.

We will discuss challenges and opportunities that come with building a data repository during periods of intense change, plans for user training, and the bright future that Princeton Data Commons presents.

ID: 408 / PR22: 3

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: CKAN, Open Source, Public Depository, FAIR Data Principle, User Community, Data Policy

Building An Open Repository for FAIR Data: Experience Sharing on Technologies, Communities, and Policies

Tyng-Ruey Chuang^{1,2,3}, Ming-Syuan Ho², Cheng-Jen Lee¹, Chia-Hsun Wang¹

¹Institute of Information Science, Academia Sinica, Taiwan; ²Research Center for Information Technology Innovation, Academia Sinica, Taiwan; ³Research Center for Humanities and Social Sciences (Center for GIS), Academia Sinica, Taiwan

We report on our progress in developing an open repository facilitating the practices of FAIR data and reproducible research. We review our efforts in the areas of technical development, community outreach, and policy dialogue. We think our experience shall be helpful to others whose undertakings have also focused on building open repositories but are similarly constrained by resources.

ID: 201 / PR22: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: InvenioRDM, institutional repositories, UX, user testing, connectivity

Challenges and opportunities when launching an institutional digital repository service in parallel with developing a data governance model and data stewardship practices

Rosa Lönnberg

KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden

The rapid development of new digital research practices has changed the ways of sharing scientific knowledge. This provides both new opportunities for sharing digital research artifacts as well as new challenges when it comes to complexity in the evolving digital landscape.

One key challenge is to enable sharing of digital research artifacts to promote research transparency for different research domains while still maintaining the legal and ethical responsibilities at the University level. Solving issues related to this key challenge requires both technical solutions as well as cultural change.

Our approach has been to work in parallel with setting-up a new digital repository while evolving a new data governance model in dialog with test-users. This dialog has also been helpful in gaining understanding on data stewardship practices and roles needed in different research communities in order to document, curate and maintain FAIR data over time. This approach also included established partnership with the InvenioRDM project to develop the open source framework used for the digital repository.

Conclusions will be presented more thoroughly during the presentation, but we see a cross-functional approach where people with different skills and experiences are engaged to contribute as necessary for enabling change to happen.

12:30 - 13:30

Lunch Break

13:30 - 15:00

24x7: Technical Solutions

Location: **Drottningporten 1**

Session Chair: **Urban Andersson**, Chalmers University of Technology

ID: 220 / 24X704: 1

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems

Keywords: harvester, alignment, dissemination

Semi-automatic submissions in the French open archive HAL: a new service for researchers

Yannick Barborini, Bénédicte Kuntziger, Philippe Chan

CCSD, CNRS, France

HAL is the multidisciplinary French national open archive for all academic documents, published or not published. HAL contains more than 1.250.000 files of articles, preprints, conference papers, images etc....

HAL is a pillar for the national open science policy. The first (2018) and the second (2021-2024) French plans for Open Science highlighted the need for HAL to simplify the deposit process for researchers, even when they publish in other open access platforms across the world, by developing an integrated self-archiving service, with automated targeted harvest of publications. This project is funded by ANR (<https://anr.fr/en/>), the French national research agency (ANR 21-ESRE-0047).

For this purpose, we have developed a service that suggests to researchers some of their documents available in other platforms, with the possibility of easily depositing them into HAL. In this talk, we will give an overview of the service, highlight how we have addressed some technical issues in order to build it and give some initial feedback of the service since its opening at the end of 2023.

ID: 238 / 24X704: 2

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Dataverse, RO-Crate, FAIR-IMPACT, Interoperability

Creating a Dataverse RO-Crate exporter with FAIR-IMPACT support

Dieuwertje Bloemen, Özgür Karadeniz

KU Leuven, Belgium

In March 2023, a call was launched by the EOSC FAIR-IMPACT project called "Support offer #2: Enabling FAIR Signposting and RO-Crate for content/metadata discovery and consumption"[1]. We decided to join the short-term support action to get expert advice on how best to integrate RO-Crate in Dataverse in a general and widely applicable way to improve the interoperability of data structure and metadata in repositories using the Dataverse software.

Due to the relatively short time span of the FAIR-IMPACT project, we focused on two major aspects; an RO-Crate previewer, and a schema.org-based RO-Crate metadata exporter. The first was relatively easy to set up, as there was already an existing open-source html previewer available. The RO-Crate metadata exporter was a bit more challenging as there was first a mapping necessary of all metadata elements to schema.org and because we wanted to ensure there was some configurability for installations that use custom metadata fields in their set-up. We decided to stick to the RO-Crate recommendation to use schema.org, as by using it whenever possible, we facilitate the interoperability with other systems or metadata management tools as well.

This is a first step in a larger project to fully integrate RO-Crate in Dataverse.

ID: 272 / 24X704: 3

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: Research data governance, repository system, space science data management and application

Data governance and application practices in NSSDC for the new paradigm

QI XU^{1,2}, Ziming ZOU^{1,2}, Jizhou TONG^{1,2}, Xiaoyan HU^{1,2}

¹National Space Science Center, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China, People's Republic of; ²National Space Science Data Center

Space science data is exploding but a large amount of scientific data is not being adequately analyzed and utilized. AI is accelerating space science data application, while still facing a series of challenges, such as the lack of data governance standards, data quality to be improved, and insufficient supply of intelligence-driven data application tools.

Data repositories are expected to play a role in improving data governance, hence, the Chinese National Space Science Data Center (NSSDC) has carried out a series of data governance practices in terms of FAIR data, open data action, data infrastructure development, data analysis and fusion tools development and data application ecosystem building, etc. Through these practices, NSSDC aims to improve the level of open data and application of space science data, providing high-quality data supply, enabling the effective use of data to mine new information and discover new knowledge. In the end of presentation, NSSDC like to share some thoughts on the future path of the new paradigm driven by data & intelligence.

ID: 283 / 24X704: 4

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems

Keywords: Institutional repository, open-source software, sustainability, data migration

From Invenio1 to DSpace7: Sustainability of an Institutional Repository in Practice

Hana Vyčítalová, Petra Černohlávková, David Gerner

National Library of Technology, Czech Republic

The National Library of Technology (NTK) has operated its institutional repository for publications and other outputs for over ten years on the open-source platform Invenio 1. With a lack of technical staff over the years, the maintenance of the repository was getting more and more complicated. By 2022, the situation was no longer sustainable, and we had to face difficult choices. To ensure the repository's sustainability, it was necessary to change the software and process the data migration. We chose DSpace 7 as it meets our requirements well. Nevertheless, there are only a few implementations of DSpace 7 so far, none of them in the Czech Republic (only version 6). In all circumstances, it meant many challenges and mistakes during the DSpace 7 implementation. Our experience with the sustainability of a repository on a short budget is very fresh. We want to share it with the community, so our mistakes don't have to be repeated. The contribution briefly describes the NTK repository context and shares the challenges and mistakes we made while implementing the chosen solution.

ID: 325 / 24X704: 5

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: digital libraries, non-textual content, digital pictures, machine learning

Orbis Pictus – book revival for cultural and creative sectors

Martin Lhotak¹, Filip Kersch¹, Petr Zabicka²

¹Library of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Czech Republic; ²Moravian Library in Brno

Collections of the Czech libraries contain a vast amount of information. Despite the dominance of textual information, a significant part of our cultural heritage is also information captured graphically, be it drawings, maps, diagrams, graphs, photographs, tables or other primarily graphic elements. As digitisation progresses, the deployment of OCR and full-text search systems is opening up hitherto hidden textual cultural heritage to the public. The aim of the presented project is to open the graphic content of digital libraries to the public in a similar way. Using machine learning methods, it will be possible to identify the graphic elements contained in digitized documents, to categorize them by type, to add contextual data to facilitate their retrieval and to extend the range of services of our digital libraries by a system for retrieving the graphic elements identified in this way. An important part of the project's outputs will be a tool for finding different images of the same persons and a database of identified persons. The project will thus result, among other things, in a significant facilitation of access by external users to graphic elements contained in library collections and their further use in other creative industries.

ID: 341 / 24X704: 6

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: DSpace 7, Repositories, Migration, RCAAP, SARI

Migrate DSpace from 5x to 7x - How do we did it in our national open access service at RCAAP

Paulo Graca¹, Fernando Ribeiro¹, Raquel Truta², Ricardo Saraiva², Paulo Lopes¹

¹FCT/FCCN, Portugal; ²University of Minho

The RCAAP network, crucial for promoting Open Science in Portugal, includes the Institutional Repository Hosting Service (SARI), which hosts 28 repositories. Facing the challenge of migrating from DSpace 5.x to DSpace 7.x, the process unfolded in phases. The creation of DSpace 7+, incorporating additional integrations, marked the initial step. A pilot project involving two institutions refined the migration process. With a focus on improved user interfaces, recent technologies, customization, and new integrations, DSpace 7.x was chosen. Despite compromises and acknowledged usability issues, the migration aimed to align with the community's needs. The ongoing evolution prioritizes aspects adding value to what DSpace delivers within the broader scientific ecosystem. Notably, lessons learned emphasize the significance of constant improvement and prioritization of features aligned with community needs.

ID: 346 / 24X704: 7

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems

Keywords: institutional repository, COAR Community Framework, self-assessment tool

Self-Assessment Tool for the COAR Community Framework

Masashi Kawai¹, Su Nee GOH², Iryna Kuchma³, Kathleen Shearer⁴, Masaharu Hayashi¹, Kazutsuna Yamaji¹

¹National Institute of Informatics; ²Nanyang Technological University; ³Electronic Information for Libraries; ⁴Confederation of Open Access Repositories

Thousands of institutions in Asia have institutional repositories, but many of them have not given sufficient attention to operational quality issues. This lack of focus may have made the institutional repositories less attractive to users. In response to this situation, we, National Institute of Informatics (NII), have chosen to use a survey based on the COAR Community Framework for Good Practices in Repositories, a set of checklists designed to measure the operational quality of repositories, aiming to raise awareness to the issues within the institutional repository community in Asia. To effectively raise awareness, conducting periodic surveys with feedback becomes crucial. However, existing survey systems pose challenges as they tend to lack a feedback function that automates the labor-intensive process of e-mailing responses, scoring answers, graphing scores, and issuing certifications for thousands of institutions. To address the issue, we have developed a self-assessment tool, a survey system featuring a feedback function that automates the process. By making the survey available to the community through the system, we aim to raise awareness extensively and enhance actual operational practices eventually.

ID: 356 / 24X704: 8
Lightning (24x7) Presentations
Topics: Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability
Keywords: Records in Contexts, Graph databases, RDF

Digital archiving using Records in Contexts

Andreas Nef¹, Thomas Bernhart²

¹On the record AB, Sweden; ²docuteam AG, Switzerland

Many organizations have gathered experience in managing/providing metadata using graphs/linked data technologies. Some months ago, the International Council on Archives finally released version 1.0 of Records in Contexts (RiC) including an ontology. We are presenting graph-based software solutions, both an archival information system as well as a repository system, using this standard.

13:30 - 15:00

Presentations: Metrics and Assessment

Location: **Drottningporten 2**

Session Chair: **Joseph Kraus**, Colorado School of Mines

ID: 214 / PR13: 1

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: reuse assessment, citation analysis, open access repositories, generalist repositories

If you build it, will they use it? Measuring usage of a global open access repository to assess impact.

Andrew Mckenna-Foster¹, Maria Cotera

Figshare, United Kingdom

The availability of shared data and non-traditional research outputs has increased dramatically over the last ten years and this corpus is growing at an exponential rate. Generalist repository platforms have matured into well-known locations to transparently share a wide range of outputs, enabling sustainable sharing and reuse of data. They have a global reach and serve researchers from a wide range of domains and research settings. However, what does the use of these open platforms actually look like? Have they helped researchers share outputs FAIRly? Is the data being reused and cited? If so, what percent of citations are other than self citations? The answers to these questions can help build a business case for research support services and resource allocation, as well as guiding platform development. They also help inform the broader conversation around how institutional repositories fit into the research landscape, democratizing data sharing and empowering global progress. In this paper we present data from one free generalist platform, examining how its global user base shares and reuses research outputs, with specific focus on linking and citations, to answer the questions above and explore its contribution to empowering global progress.

ID: 254 / PR13: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: SwePub; national bibliography database; open access, Swedish research

Can the National Repository of Sweden Be Utilized for In-Depth Bibliometric Analysis: Unlocking Insights into Swedish Research

A I M Jakaria Rahman¹, Marco Schirone^{1,2}

¹Chalmers University of Technology, Sweden; ²University of Borås, Sweden

Investigating national repositories is crucial as they play a pivotal role in shaping the accessibility and interconnectedness of global research. This investigation aims to offer insights into the impact and effectiveness of SwePub, Sweden's national bibliographic database. Through bibliometric exploration spanning 8-years (2015-2022), this study employs SwePub's data to unveil publication trends in open access, shedding light on the preferences of Sweden-affiliated researchers in disseminating their research through non-open access, gold open access, and green open access channels. This paper advocates for a more distinct classification of open access beyond a binary categorization, providing a detailed representation of Sweden's contributions to various forms of open access, such as gold and green open access, and their impact on disseminating academic knowledge. The findings on international and national collaboration stress the importance of global and national networks in collaborative research. However, data retrieval requires integrating citation data from databases like Open Alex to enhance in-depth bibliometric analysis. This paper concludes by proposing the transformation of SwePub into a more comprehensive resource, elevating its utility for institutional or national-level bibliometric analysis. The results contain insightful information for academic institutions, policymakers, and the scholarly community.

ID: 348 / PR13: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Data Visualization, Scientific Information Systems, BrCris (Brazil), Open Science.

Visual Panorama: The Various Facets of Data Visualization of the Brazilian Scientific Research Ecosystem with Aid from BrCris

Washington Luís Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo¹, Thiago Magela Rodrigues Dias², Patrícia da Silva Neubert³, Adilson Luiz Pinto³

¹Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Brazil; ²Centro Federal de Educação Tecnológica de Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), Brazil; ³Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina (UFSC), Brasil

Brazil currently hosts several institutional platforms, such as the Lattes Platform, Sucupira Platform, Transparency Portal, Catalog/Library of Theses and Dissertations, and Industrial Property Bank. These platforms were created with the aim of providing data in a centralized and updated manner on the academic, scientific, and technological performance of its researchers. Therefore, the BrCris Project aims to establish a unique model for organizing scientific information across the entire Brazilian research ecosystem. Among the agents of this ecosystem are researchers, projects, infrastructures, laboratories and research institutions, funders, in addition to research results expressed mainly through scientific publications, theses, dissertations, scientific data sets, software and patents. This work aims to present how BrCris has contributed to the process of aggregating platforms and data visualization, with the aim of promoting access and visualization of science. As a result, it is possible to visualize, access, export and evaluate integrated data from different sources, enabling the understanding of scientific and academic information, as well as the analysis of aggregated data from different perspectives.

ID: 379 / PR13: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Africa, Institutional Repository, IRs, visibility analysis, global impact

Visibility Analysis of African Institutional Repositories for Global Impact

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¹Hezekiah Oluwasanmi Library, Obafemi Awolowo University, Nigeria; ²National Library of Nigeria, Nigeria

The research landscape in Africa holds immense potential, yet its scholarly output often struggles to reach global audiences. Institutional repositories (IRs) emerge as beacons of hope, a platform to showcase African research and development as well as intellectualism and propel it them into the international spotlight. However, the effectiveness of IRs in achieving these goals depends on their visibility, which in the case of African repositories is very low. This paper delves into the trajectories of IR development by selected universities in each of the sub-regions of Africa. Using mixed methods, a visibility analysis was conducted using interviews, case studies and key metrics such as evolution, institutional policies, awareness, Authors' attitudes and responsiveness, downloads, citations and global impacts. Qualitative and quantitative data analysis were utilized. Findings revealed that although visibility is relatively low on global terrains, it showed an impressive, vibrant and competitive landscape of African IRs. Despite challenges such as insufficient researcher awareness, inadequate infrastructure and limited funding, the repositories are increasingly promoting global engagement with African scholarship, discoverability and collaboration beyond national borders. Recommendations were made for supportive policies, sustainable funding, enhanced awareness for researchers, ethical considerations, standardized metadata and platforms for knowledge sharing.

<p>13:30 - 15:00</p>	<p>Presentations: Problem Solving Location: Drottningporten 3 Session Chair: Cecilia Granell, Chalmers University of Technology</p>
	<p>ID: 195 / PR14: 1 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Climate Justice, Responsible Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Community Standards, AI, DevOps, Licenses</p> <p>Creating a better balance: the need for tools and practices to combat AI harvests and resource flooding in repository environments</p> <p>Allison Kelly Sherrick, Diego Alberto Pino Navarro Metropolitan New York Library Council, United States of America</p> <p>We have entered a new era when the internet is fueled by massive AI and ML applications, which has significant consequences for the field of open repositories. The resources required to provide normal, quality repository interactions alongside unregulated consumption of data and resources by AI-powered bots is increasingly more tenuous and difficult to accommodate, and challenges our well established ideas of what openness means. Our Digital Services Team at METRO has been implementing a multifaceted approach to combating the rise of AI bot harvest waves that has been escalating over the past year. This approach includes multiple behind the scenes DevOps and code based tactics, and requires high machine and human resources to maintain and consistently scale up as AI bots become more sophisticated and well-resourced. We propose the implementation of standardized "no-AI" or "regulated AI" use licenses and realistic DevOps practices that could be applied in open repository environments across the globe. We cannot expect the commercial industry of AI/ML data mining to regulate itself, and we need to create consensus in our own community for combating this significant challenge.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 199 / PR14: 2 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Sustainable open-source software, GitHub repositories, community structure, community smells, csDetector, social network analysis</p> <p>What are the characteristic community smells influencing the sustainability of open-source repository software communities?</p> <p>Tomasz Neugebauer¹, Pierre Lasou², Pamela Carson¹ ¹Concordia University, Canada; ²Université Laval, Canada</p> <p>In this presentation, we will summarize some emerging methods used to characterize problems (i.e., "community smells") that open-source software communities face which will affect their sustainability. We will describe the type of information that can be extracted from community analysis tools that analyze GitHub repositories and present the results of running one such diagnostic tool on several open repositories projects: DSpace, Dataverse, EPrints, Islandora, Samvera, Archivematica, and OJS. The motivating objective for this work is to understand if tools can be used by libraries to better understand the open source communities that they rely on, and ultimately, to use that understanding to help address existing issues or to make strategic decisions about adoption.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 289 / PR14: 3 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Scholarly graph, deduplication, repository integration, CORE Dashboard</p> <p>Automatic detection of duplicate records in institutional repositories</p> <p>Matteo Cancellieri, Anton Zhuk, Valerii Budko, Ekaterine Chxaidze, Viktoriia Pavlenko, Petr Knoth Open University, United Kingdom</p> <p>The prevalence of multiple copies of articles in repositories presents a significant challenge in maintaining the integrity and clarity of the research graph. Issues such as processing errors and lack of communication between co-authors contribute to the existence of duplicates and near-duplicate records. The CORE Dashboard Versions and Duplicates module was developed to address this issue by providing an innovative tool to identify versions and duplicates within repositories. The system facilitates side-by-side comparison and labelling of versions and exact duplicates for removal.</p> <p>This presentation will report on the experience and the collective feedback from repository managers and give an update on the efforts to integrate duplicate and near-duplicate matching into the deposit workflow.</p>
<p>13:30 - 15:00</p>	<p>Roundtable Discussions Location: Brevsorterarsalen Session Chair: Nora Mulvaney, Toronto Metropolitan University</p>
	<p>ID: 310 / RT01: 1 Roundtable Discussion <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Research Data Management and Curation <i>Keywords:</i> Research data repository, Research data retention policy, Repository administration</p> <p>Creating Transparent Retention Policies for Data Repositories to Ensure Long-Term Sustainability for the Research Community</p> <p>Santi Thompson¹, Christina Chan-Park², Laura Sare³, Andrea Schorr⁴, Michael Shensky⁵, Xuan Zhou⁶ ¹University of Houston, United States of America; ²Baylor University, United States of America; ³Texas A&M University, United States of America; ⁴University of Texas Health San Antonio, United States of America; ⁵University of Texas at Austin, United States of America; ⁶Texas State University, United States of America</p> <p>Members of the Texas Data Repository Steering Committee, who represent a diverse range of data management and curation experts at a variety of public and private academic libraries in Texas, U.S., are working together to develop a research data retention policy. While establishing the policy and guidelines, members of the ad-hoc working group recognized that many institutions with research data repositories will face the challenge of establishing research data retention policies. Beyond a lack of common practices to model local policies, institutions will also face numerous hurdles, including adopting a policy that is: flexible enough to address a growing diversity of research data, aligned with evolving funding agency and local institutional mandates, and economically sustainable over time. This roundtable will focus on better understanding what research data retention policies are and how they are formed.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 319 / RT01: 2 Roundtable Discussion <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Best practice, advocacy, support</p> <p>Do as I say, not as I do: when best practice and reality don't agree and what (if anything) can be done about it</p> <p>Leigh Stork¹, Nora Mulvaney² ¹Aston University; ²Toronto Metropolitan University</p> <p>As individuals who work with repositories to facilitate open research (including open access and open research data), we have all seen cases where 'champions' of openness deliberately or inadvertently ignore best practice guidelines for making outputs and research data freely accessible. We may, in fact, be the guilty party ourselves in some instances because of resource pressures.</p> <p>During this roundtable we will discuss the common issues that prevent us, and the communities we support, from promoting research transparency by actively following current best practice in repository use. Examples for discussion include: 'Data available upon reasonable request', articles about open access/open research not being made open access, pressures related to repository staffing and skills, etc. Through anecdotal examples we will share our experiences of these common blockers to repository best practice and explore potential solutions that participants can use in the future.</p>
<p>15:00 - 15:30</p>	<p>Coffee Break</p>

15:30 - 17:00	<p>Presentations: Policy Impact on Repositories Location: Drottningporten 1 Session Chair: Emily Bongiovanni, Carnegie Mellon University</p>
	<p>ID: 221 / PR16: 1 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems <i>Keywords:</i> equity, green open access, impact, integrations</p> <p>Green Open Access - Institutional Repositories fulfilling their whole purpose Mark Hahnel, Adrian Clark Digital Science, United Kingdom</p> <p>In repositories, we have the tools to power open access in a way that is cost effective and equitable to all. We have the tools to re-engineer how academic publishing operates. This has only been amplified by the growing global reach of the web. However, since 2011, the uptake of Gold vs Green Open access globally indicates that Green Open Access is losing the race for significance. Gold Open Access, while expensive, offers a more streamlined publication process, greater visibility, and often, a more polished platform for research dissemination. This has led to a growing divide in access to academic resources, where well-funded research is more readily available than research from less affluent sources.</p> <p>This presentation will highlight ways for librarians to demonstrate to research offices, the opportunities for more impact in their research and reduced publishing budgets via Green Open Access. We will investigate the differences in citation counts and altmetric scores across different formats of academic publishing, from closed access, to gold and green. The talk will highlight the integrations that repositories can use to superpower their repository submissions.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 259 / PR16: 2 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency <i>Keywords:</i> Equity, federal agency, open access, transparency</p> <p>Equity in Open Access to Scientific Research Results: Insights from Federal Agency Responses to the Nelson Memorandum Policy Jwan Khisro, Katrina Fenlon University of Maryland, United States of America</p> <p>To empower progress, it is vital to ensure that scientific research results are made transparent and freely available for all members of society. Open access is intended to solve issues that have long constrained scholarly communication and research advancement, namely accessibility, affordability, and equity. Yet, there is little agreement among funding and research agencies, policymakers, repository managers, and data producers about what equity means in open access. This presentation reports on a study currently in development by a collaborative team of researchers at the University of Maryland, College Park, and representatives from the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) National Agricultural Library (NAL). It offers insights on the meaning of equity about open access to research results, based on two sources: (1) a literature review of the concept of equity in the context of open access; and (2) an empirical analysis of how federal agencies, as a key set of stakeholders, are responding to the requirement for equity in the 2022 White House Office of Science and Technology Policy Memorandum on "Ensuring Free, Immediate, and Equitable Access to Federally Funded Research" (Nelson, 2022). The preliminary analysis indicates little consensus on the equity concept in open access to research results.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 170 / PR16: 3 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Climate Justice, Research Data Management and Curation <i>Keywords:</i> data curation, peer-to-peer, code, simulation data, scientific image, geospatial data, funder requirements, collaboration, grant funding</p> <p>How it started; how it's going: Developing Specialized Data Curation Training to Address Needed Expertise in Focused Areas Wanda Marsolek University of Minnesota, United States of America</p> <p>This presentation will provide a very brief overview of the Data Curation Network (DCN) and the IMLS funded project, "Developing Specialized Data Curation Training to Address Needed Expertise in Focused Areas" (RE-252343-OLS-22). The majority of the presentation will focus on the experience of the simulation data cohort mentor, what went into developing curriculum for technical data types, and how other organizations or groups may go about working towards bridging the gaps in curation to further the field. The four specialized data types (code, scientific data, geo-spatial data, and simulation data) are integral to climate justice work. Training data curators how to curate the data will allow more reuse. Developing training materials, testing them out, editing and sharing globally will help those who are new to specialized data become more skilled as we all work to promote research transparency and elevate underrepresented communities when we make our teams more inclusive and data more FAIR. Feedback from the instructional cohorts as well as attendees of the pilot workshop will be shared to help others learn from what we may have done better.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 343 / PR16: 4 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> NIH, Generalist Repositories, Community, Transparency, Development, Biomedical Data, Open Access, Data Sharing, FAIR data, Metadata</p> <p>Empowering Global Progress: GREI Coopetition's Role in Standardizing Transparency, Community, and Sustainability Initiatives Sonia Maria BARBOSA¹, Mark HAHNEL², Kristi HOLMES³ ¹The Dataverse Project; ²Figshare; ³Zenodo</p> <p>role in the data-sharing landscape. In January 2023, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) of the United States started requiring most of the 300,000 researchers and 2,500 institutions it funds annually to include a data management and sharing plan and to make research data publicly available. Towards this end, the NIH launched the Generalist Repository Ecosystem Initiative (GREI) with seven generalist repositories working together to support NIH data sharing and discovery through consistent metadata, common metrics, and training on using these repositories. During this presentation, our speakers will discuss:</p> <p>The GREI program, its mission, and goals</p> <p>What the GREI coopetition has accomplished to date and incorporated to support research transparency and how communities worldwide can benefit from these developments and models.</p> <p>How "co-opetition" amongst repositories is creating a model of data transparency, community, and sustainability others can implement.</p> <p>How researchers around the world can benefit from the program</p>
15:30 - 17:00	<p>Presentations: Repository Trust and Certification Location: Drottningporten 2 Session Chair: Tomas Lunden, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences</p>
	<p>ID: 240 / PR17: 1 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation <i>Keywords:</i> Repository certification, active preservation, cts, Nestor</p> <p>What defines trust? Can general-purpose repositories be certified at all? Kai Wörner Universität Hamburg, Germany</p> <p>When deciding on a repository to deposit your research data, certificates are meant to be helping with the decision. They claim to indicate whether a repository is "trustworthy" by focusing on technical specifications, implemented procedures and workflows as well as institutional backup. Research data repositories that take care of the "long tail" of research data and do not focus on certain domains (thus not having an estimation on what kind of data they can expect), have a problem when trying to get their repositories certified,</p>

though: The predominant repository certification programs require a process of “active preservation” to be present in the repository workflow, which many repositories in general will never be able to implement. The presentation will try to ask whether criteria like active preservation are valid indicators for trustworthiness or whether other aspects might be more important in practice.

ID: 296 / PR17: 2

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: archiving workflows, FAIR data, repository systems, research data management, archaeology

Towards a Trusted Domain Repository: Rebuilding the Archaeological Map of the Czech Republic on the Fedora Platform

David Novák

Institute of Archaeology of the CAS, Prague, Czech Republic

The presentation discusses the comprehensive reimplement of the Archaeological Map of the Czech Republic (AMCR). The outdated technologies and platforms of AMCR led to the decision to renew the system. The chosen solution involved integrating the Fedora 6 platform, based on the OCFL standard, to address issues of quality, sustainability, and secure data storage. The selection of Fedora was driven by the need for a low-complexity platform with an efficient back-end, and the use of OCFL ensured future-proof repository content. The AMCR, designed for archaeological heritage management, originally faced challenges such as low performance and security issues. The new implementation is based entirely on open source solutions, using the Python-based Django framework and the PostgreSQL database. Data storage now follows the OCFL format, mediated by Fedora via the REST API. The presentation highlights the benefits of this approach, emphasizing development flexibility and system modularity, while ensuring data consistency at multiple levels. The reimplement aims to achieve a user-friendly, modular system with a stable backend that meets the criteria for secure long-term storage of digital data. The changes are consistent with the goal of certifying AMCR as a trusted domain digital repository, addressing aspects of FAIR data and long-term preservation.

ID: 388 / PR17: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: CoreTrustSeal, Trustworthy repositories, Certification process, Fiocruz

Lessons learned to prepare for CoreTrustSeal certification: the case of Arca Dados

Luciana Monteiro-Krebs^{1,2}, Rafael Port da Rocha², Maria de Fatima Moreira Martins Correa¹, Vanessa de Arruda Jorge¹

¹Fundação Oswaldo Cruz (Fiocruz), Brazil; ²Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil

Applying for CoreTrustSeal certification challenged and enriched Arca Dados, Fiocruz's data repository. Aligning its practices with CoreTrustSeal's rigorous criteria, while showcasing the strength of its existing framework within Fiocruz's robust infrastructure, proved insightful. Key lessons learned include: Aligning repository and institutional practices required referencing over 100 documents, showcasing Fiocruz's commitment to data governance and trustworthiness; Specific CoreTrustSeal requirements linked to legal aspects and IT infrastructure, demanded close attention due to their alignment with institutional policies and procedures; The Arca Dados Operative Plan and Workflow proved valuable evidence for multiple requirements, demonstrating thorough planning and process implementation; Deposit involves collaboration between the curation team, Fiocruz bodies, and domain experts, ensuring diverse perspectives and expertise; Pre-existing terms of use, rights agreements, and license choices (CC-BY) facilitated the R02 requirement, highlighting the benefits of prior planning; and interviews during deposit provide insights into community practices and inform digital preservation strategies. Overall, the CoreTrustSeal application process proved valuable for Arca Dados, solidifying its commitment to data quality, trustworthiness, and accessibility while identifying areas for further improvement. This experience offers valuable insights for other institutional repositories, particularly those within complex research institutions like Fiocruz.

ID: 215 / PR17: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: Research Data Management, Hyrax-Based Repository, User Participation in Development, Trust in Repositories

Creating Trust in Research Data Repositories via a user-driven implementation: Case study of a hyrax-based, institutional data repository

Alexander Esser¹, Johannes Frenzel¹, Veronika Josenhans¹, Tobias Otto¹, Marlene Pacharra¹, Paul Walk², Nina O.C. Winter¹

¹Ruhr University Bochum, Germany; ²Antleaf Ltd., UK

Repositories play a key role for the long-term access and publication of research data. However, there are cultural barriers for the use of research data repositories, especially for data which are not (yet) intended for public access. In certain scientific disciplines there are renowned repositories available, in other disciplines there is a lack of research data management infrastructure. For the latter, institutional infrastructures come into play. We report a case study of a research data repository (ReSeeD) operated by Ruhr University Bochum (Germany) and based on the Hyrax platform of the Samvera community. Adaptations to the open source platform were made to lower the cultural barrier for data deposit and direct linking with relevant metadata: A fine-grained role and rights management enables tailored visibility of data. A multi-step and tiered review workflow is prerequisite for 10 years of preservation or publication with DOI. Easy authentication even beyond institutional affiliation is mediated via ORCID. The implementation was carried out in close collaboration between central IT, library and a research use case. In a first stage, ReSeeD was brought into service late 2023 and is intended to serve as infrastructure for the about 6000 researchers of the university and external project partners.

15:30 - 17:00

Presentations: Use of Persistent Identifiers

Location: **Drottningporten 3**

Session Chair: **Lisa Lamont**, San Diego State University

ID: 395 / PR18: 1

Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: reference matching, Crossref, metadata

A Large-Scale Reference Matching for Records in Japanese Institutional Repositories using Crossref REST API

Chifumi Nishioka, Jun-ichi Onami, Kazutsuna Yamaji

National Institute of Informatics, Japan

Persistent identifiers such as DOIs are essential for scholarly records for e.g., the discovery of related resources and citations. Therefore, repository managers and scholars are expected to input a DOI when they submit a manuscript (e.g., author's accepted manuscript (AAM)) to a repository. However, sometimes DOIs are missing in the records of repositories. In this work, we perform reference matching for journal articles or conference papers in CiNii Research to identify their DOIs. CiNii Research is the Japanese national discovery platform for scholarly information and contains a lot of records missing a DOI originating from institutional repositories. We conducted a reference matching for 110,477 records using the Crossref API. As a result, we observed that the Crossref REST API returns a truly matching record more than 95% of the time when the score exceeds 120. The Crossref records that scored high but were determined not to be a match include e.g., authors' responses during peer review. If the Crossref REST API returns multiple records with high scores, we may avoid mismatch by referring to the type of a record (e.g., review) and other non-bibliographic information. This work helps repository managers who attempt to perform reference matching.

ID: 275 / PR18: 2

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: persistent identifiers, URNs, resolution services, FAIRCORE4EOSC

URNs as persistent identifiers for repositories: resolution services and user networks

Jyrki Ilva, Emma Pietarila, Ulriika Vihervalli

National Library of Finland, Finland

This presentation explores the use of Uniform Resource Names (URNs), specifically URN:NBNS, as persistent identifiers (PID) in the repository context. URNs are a standards-based identifier system, which has been around since the 1990s. The National Library of Finland (NLF) has been providing a national URN resolution service at urn.fi since 2007. The ease of implementation and cost-free nature of URNs has led to the adoption of URN-based persistent addresses at all Finnish institutional repositories.

URN:NBN identifiers are currently in active use in 13 European countries, with the national library usually providing services and coordination. However, as there is no organization overseeing the use of URNs on a global level, there has been little international cooperation in this area, and the profile of URN:NBN:s remains relatively low compared to some of the other PID systems, especially DOIs.

As part of the EU-funded FAIRCORE4EOSC project, NLF has started to contact and interview the other national URN service providers. There are plans to foster collaboration by organising a URN:NBN webinar and producing a URN:NBN landscape study in 2024. The Meta Resolver service, which is being developed within the FAIRCORE4EOSC project, may also provide steps towards improved interoperability in PID resolution, including, importantly, URN:NBNs.

ID: 350 / PR18: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Data Integration, Scientific Information Systems, Scientific Production, Persistent Identifier

Data Repository Integration Strategies with the Aid of Persistent Identifiers in the BrCris Project

Washington Luis Ribeiro de Carvalho Segundo¹, Thiago Magela Rodrigues Dias², Patricia da Silva Neubert³, Fábio Lorensi do Canto³

¹Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Brazil; ²Centro Federal de Educação Tecnológica de Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), Brazil; ³Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina (UFSC), Brasil

Considering the entire process of curating the data to be collected, integrated and analyzed in the context of the BrCris project, a strategy for generating identifiers is necessary. Such identifiers are important because all collected data is mapped to entities, previously identified, in which it is necessary to identify them in a unique way, taking into account the entire processing process to be carried out, especially the process of disambiguation and deduplication of data. To this end, a computational library, using the Python programming language, was proposed in which it is responsible for generating BrCris Identifiers, created with the aim of pre-disambiguating the data, avoiding duplicate entities in the set to be analyzed. For each set of data to be analyzed, a strategy for generating identifiers was considered. This strategy aims to use as little information as possible that is extracted, but which can generate, with a satisfactory level of confidence, unique identifiers, which will be used in several future stages.

ID: 363 / PR18: 4

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Integration, Automation, Sustainability, PIDs

It already knows! A prototype PID-optimised workflow for a repository

Rory McNicholl, Will Fyson, Eleanor Dumbill

CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom

Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) are a key part of scholarly communications infrastructure and ensuring that they can be generated and used to represent all parts of the research process has been a long-term goal of the repository community. In the UK a recent national PID strategy has sought to distil knowledge and best practice in this area and establish a spine of key PID services that will ease the flow of information between research related services and organisations within the UK, while also enhancing access to UK research from around the world. Taking a lead from the UK PID strategy, we explore the it's potential with a practical application within an institutional repository. Is it possible to realise the benefits of efficiency, automation, data quality and system integration, that the strategy promises?

15:30 - 17:00

Presentations: Supporting Research Transparency

Location: **Brevsorterarsalen 3**

Session Chair: **Katie Mika**, Harvard University

ID: 137 / PR25: 1

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: Open Research Data Repository, Research Data Management, Agricultural Research Institute, Research transparency, Data Curation

Open Research Data Repositories in Promoting Research Transparency and a Sustainable future in Research Data Management

Emily Jeruto Ng'eno

Moi University, Kenya

Open Research Data Repositories (ORDR) is a throtlehold in promoting research transparency and Research Data Management (RDM). ORDR can be established and managed through facilitation of RDM governance by adoption of appropriate technical standards, practices and architecture that will necessitate management, promotion of research transparency, sharing and reuse of research data. The agricultural research institutes in Kenya generate a lot of research data, however, little is known about the mechanisms for the management of such data especially with regard to curation, ORDR that promote research transparency, reuse, and sharing. The purpose of this study is to examine ORDR in promoting research transparency and a sustainable future in RDM in Kenya's agricultural research institutes with the view to proposing interventions to improve open research data repositories in order to facilitate research transparency, management, sharing and reuse of agricultural research output. The findings of the study revealed that inadequate and outdated policies that guide the establishment and management of ORDR, inadequate awareness and advocacy on the use and benefits of ORDR by all stakeholders, minimal utilization of ORDR. The study recommends: a formal and robust data governance framework; revision of RDM policy and regulation; establishment of awareness, advocacy and data literacy programs.

ID: 292 / PR25: 2

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems

Keywords: retrieval augmented generation, LLMs, AI, question-answering, open repositories, recommender systems

CORE GPT: Large Language Models for question-answering over open access research

David Pride, Matteo Cancellieri, Petr Knoth

The Open University, United Kingdom

This paper introduces CORE-GPT, an innovative platform that combines large language models (LLMs) with 34 million open-access scientific articles available through CORE. Addressing the challenge of generating credible, well-cited answers, the platform significantly reduces the potential for "hallucinations" in AI-generated text. Evaluated across the top 20 scientific domains in CORE, CORE-GPT demonstrates its effectiveness in producing reliable, in-depth answers with citations and links to original research articles. Initially designed to complement CORE Search, the tool expands the capabilities of the CORE services including recommendations and enhancing the user experience in academic libraries. By incorporating citations, links, and open-access articles, CORE-GPT fosters trustworthiness, efficiency, broad coverage, and promotes open access research, making it a highly useful tool for researchers and practitioners.

ID: 230 / PR25: 3

Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Climate Justice, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: biodiversity data repository, persistent identifier, DOI-Digital Object Identifier

Understanding DOI attribution in biodiversity repositories: A Brazilian case study

Laura Vilela Rodrigues Rezende¹, Geisa Muller de Campos Ribeiro¹, Maria das Graças Monteiro Castro¹, Cassia Oliveira¹, Fabiano Couto Corrêa², Carolina Howard Felcissimo³, Keila Elizabeth Macfadem Juarez³, Clara Baringo Fonseca³, Yohana Pereira Ditzel³

¹Universidade Federal de Goiás, Brazil; ²Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil; ³Rede Nacional de Pesquisa, Brazil

	<p>The data sharing definitions and openness must consider, additionally, issues of institutional interest, national sovereignty, intra- and extra-country asymmetries and of reciprocity, in order to avoid increasing inequalities in the scientific and technology and population access to knowledge. In biodiversity context, Brazil has a huge relevance once the country occupies almost half of South America and is the country with the greatest biodiversity in the world. The repository SiBBR was developed as the Brazilian national repository of data and information on biodiversity, responsible for organizing, indexing, storing and making available data and information about biodiversity and Brazilian ecosystems, providing subsidies for scientific researches and government management related to conservation and sustainable use. This is a Brazilian case study that aims to bring out the challenges involved in understanding DOI attribution in biodiversity repositories. How DOI attribution to biodiversity materials in SiBBR can work as unique and persistent identifiers, allowing a relevant increase in the citations and visibility of Brazilian biodiversity data. Once the relevant context of SiBBR, serving as the Brazilian national GBIF node, it is mandatory to implement best practices in the SiBBR repository, for instance, including better characterization, identification, location and (re)use of data published.</p>
	<p>ID: 380 / PR25: 4 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems <i>Keywords:</i> Sustainable Development Goals, repository management, policy development, community engagement</p> <p>The UN Digital Library: Chartering a path forward Meg Wacha United Nations Dag Hammarskjöld Library</p> <p>The planning of information services – the planning of a library – at the United Nations (UN) began with the planning of the international organization itself. Initially established to provide research and information services to support the participation of Member States at the United Nations, the mandate of the UN Libraries, including the flagship Dag Hammarskjöld Library at the Headquarters in New York, has expanded alongside the work of the Organization.</p> <p>This presentation will detail the activities and development of the United Nations Digital Library, a repository that collects and provides public access to the documents, publications, and work of the United Nations. However, providing access to information is not just a core activity of the Secretariat, it is recognized as a human right advanced by the Organization. Therefore, this presentation will also provide key actions that librarians, repository managers, and developers can take to connect with the work of the United Nations and advance human rights and the Sustainable Development Goals through their local communities and repositories.</p>
<p>19:00 - 23:00</p>	<p>Conference Dinner Location: Kajskjul 8 Read more!</p>
<p>Date: Thursday, 06/June/2024</p>	
<p>08:30 - 14:00</p>	<p>Registration</p>
<p>09:00 - 10:30</p>	<p>24x7: Integrations for Sustainability and Transparency Location: Drottningporten 1 Session Chair: Elizabeth Krznarich, DataCite</p>
	<p>ID: 134 / 24X703: 1 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Strategic planning, facilitation, diverse teams</p> <p>We Can Work It Out: Cross-Functional Collaboration on Repository Strategy Deb Verhoff New York University, United States of America</p> <p>The New York University Division of Libraries and NYU Information Technology collaborate to provide repository services for research. Following the launch of a new data repository in 2023, a working group formed to assess and make a recommendation for whether or not to merge institutional repository services into a single platform and service team. This presentation will focus on facilitation: how a team composed of developers, scholarly communication librarians and data curation librarians worked together on this charge.</p>
	<p>ID: 236 / 24X703: 2 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Dataverse, Community governance, Open-source sustainability</p> <p>Creating a sustainable open-source repository community with Dataverse Dieuwertje Bloemen¹, Rene Belsø², Philipp Conzett³, Dimitri Szabo⁴ ¹KU Leuven, Belgium; ²DeiC (Danish e-Infrastructure Cooperation); ³UiT The Arctic University of Norway; ⁴INRAE</p> <p>Dataverse is an open-source repository software that has a community that has continued to grow over the last couple of years. With this community growth, challenges also appeared for the Dataverse community due to the variety of software deployments across countries, domains, and types of organizations, all having different needs and requirements.</p> <p>To try and find a sustainable way to keep growing while continuing to be a tight-knit community, the Dataverse Sustainability Working Group was established in the Fall of 2023. The mission of the working group is to provide evidence-based, community-reviewed, and consensus-based recommendations on how to sustain and grow the Dataverse community and how to ensure that the Dataverse software will continue to be maintained and developed in a way that benefits the user community as a whole in a long-term perspective in a sustainable way.</p> <p>During this lightning talk we would like to present the work we've done so far, from analyses and stakeholder consultation. The Open Repositories conference offers a timely opportunity to also get the outsider's perspective on these matters and challenges as well as exchange experiences from other communities that have gone or are going through the same process.</p>
	<p>ID: 307 / 24X703: 3 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Transformative Agreements, Costs, Metadata</p> <p>Transparency of payments for Open Access – Extending the metadata set with contract and payment details Julia Bartlewski¹, Christoph Broschinski¹, Gernot Deinger², Dirk Pieper¹, Bianca Schweighofer², Colin Sippel², Lisa-Marie Stein³, Alexander Wagner³, Silke Weisheit² ¹University of Bielefeld, Germany; ²University of Regensburg, Germany; ³DESY, Germany</p> <p>The talk highlights the importance of repositories in the Open Access publishing landscape and addresses the transparency challenges associated with diverse payment models. The authors propose a solution through the OpenCost project, introducing a new "contract" record type with a dedicated metadata schema in repositories. This schema includes cost data and unique identifiers, allowing for the direct linkage of publications to specific contracts. The approach provides a means to transparently track the financial aspects of publishing, offering insights into expenditures for Open Access. By referencing contracts in the metadata, the system accommodates large transformative agreements, enabling a comprehensive overview of costs related to publications at a national and institutional level. This enhancement ensures financial transparency when all data is shared under a free license, contributing to a better understanding of the transformation process in scholarly publishing.</p>
	<p>ID: 311 / 24X703: 4 Lightning (24x7) Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability <i>Keywords:</i> Dissemination of scholarship, journal publishing, scholar-led publishing</p> <p>Twenty years of quality assurance: five lessons Dominic Mitchell DOAJ, Sweden</p>

DOAJ sits at the intersection of transparency, community and sustainability. Although primarily an index of gold open access journals, we're seeing more and more platforms apply to be indexed. Is this the beginning of a blurring of boundaries? If so, what can platforms and repositories learn from our twenty years of experience regarding quality assurance and trust? Our lightning talk highlights five things that might be relevant for the future of repositories and platforms.

ID: 351 / 24X703: 5

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: At global level, open science is in situation of transition to maximize openness of data and research outputs financed with public funds in repositories, and to ensure this trend is necessary to implement information organization processes to data and res

Metadata for Creative Commons Licenses to Open Science Repositories: analysis of implementation

Juan Miguel Palma Peña

National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM), Mexico

At global level, open science is in situation of transition to maximize openness of data and research outputs financed with public funds in repositories, and to ensure this trend is necessary to implement information organization processes to data and research outputs, such as standards, metadata and FAIR principles in order to ensuring reproducibility and sharing those goods on various platforms. The aim of this document is to study some main metadata schemes that are currently used to organize logically and in a structured way Creative Commons Licenses to justify openness of research data, and based on analyzing factors, attributes and features of such metadata schemas foster implement principles of findable, access, interoperability and reusability unrestricted of such resources in repositories. Methodology for this analysis is carried out with methods theoretical and pragmatically, in which factors of open science are analyzed based on specialized literature and to prove assumptions raised carry out a content analysis of implementation of attributes of open licenses based in three main metadata schemas, such as OpenAIRE, Research Data Alliance, Dublin Core. A general conclusion is that organization of research data with metadata will be an element that will create right conditions for data sharing to become a standard.

ID: 357 / 24X703: 6

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Research Transparency

Keywords: General data repository, promote research transparency, integrations with external systems.

A Practice of Science Data Bank on Promote the transparency of research

Lulu JIANG

Computer Network Information Center, Chinese Academy of Sciences, China, People's Republic of

Data sharing is considered one of the effective practical means to enhance research transparency. Data repositories are pivotal digital infrastructure in fostering this.

But the recognition and practice of data sharing among researchers are generally insufficient. This requires multiple efforts to jointly promote policies, standards, infrastructure service capabilities, and incentive mechanisms.

As a generalist data repository, Science Data Bank (ScienceDB) offers free services to the global community for sharing and dissemination of non-traditional research outputs, such as datasets and codes. To foster the practice of open data, the repository integrates with a variety of external systems, including preprint servers, manuscript submission systems, and data management tools. Through these integrations, Science Data Bank streamlines the data sharing process across diverse research outputs, linking datasets to preprints, manuscripts, and published articles. This proposal outlines the integration endeavors undertaken by ScienceDB and showcases their service offerings.

These integrations have many positive impacts on disseminate the best practice of data sharing and foster the research transparency.

ID: 360 / 24X703: 7

Lightning (24x7) Presentations

Topics: Underrepresented Communities

Keywords: PIDs, grant program, global participation

ORCID Global Participation Fund: Improving equity of access to research infrastructure in under-represented regions

Lombe Tembo

ORCID, Zambia

ORCID's Global Participation Fund (GPF) was developed to remedy current gaps in organisational participation in ORCID, and PIDs in general, in countries that lack capabilities or resources. The GPF is aimed at benefiting organizations in regions that are under-represented, especially in countries with low- and lower-middle-income economies (as defined by the World Bank). In these Focus Communities of the GPF, we aim to provide funds to: i) foster the development of ORCID Communities of Practice, working with local partners who can build understanding and use of ORCID in local contexts; and ii) create and enhance technical integrations to support the realization of the benefits provided by the use of ORCID. Since the launch of the GPF, we have awarded 14 grants in 3 cycles and this lightning presentation will provide an overview of the GPF as well as an update on the awarded projects.

09:00 - 10:30

Developer Track Session 3

Location: **Drottningporten 2**

Session Chair: **Jonas Gilbert**, University of Borås

ID: 249 / DV03: 1

Developer Track

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation

Keywords: data repositories, virtual research environments, integration, transfer

Repositories and Computation: Crossover Episode

Maximilian Moser, Martin Weise, Sotirios Tsepelakis, Tomasz Miksa, Andreas Rauber

TU Wien, Austria

Research increasingly becomes data-driven, with substantial amounts of information being generated and analyzed to produce new insights and discoveries. Since Virtual Research Environments (VRE) like JupyterHub [1] are becoming more available, the audience that uses these compute resources becomes more heterogeneous too, demanding seamless identity management, datasource integration and high availability from VRE service providers. To make VRE research outputs more FAIR, they can be deposited in dedicated research data repositories. At TU Wien, we provide two different research data repositories [2,3] for publication of research data results, and Jupyter [4] for data processing as part of our VRE.

In order to improve user experience, we are building a library to be used in the Jupyter notebooks that allows researchers to use datasets directly in the VRE seamlessly provided by the repositories in the background, abstracted from the researcher.

Because the library only depends on public APIs, it is not tied to our VRE and can be used in other deployments as well. Further, we aim to keep the design of the library intentionally simple so that it can be extended with support for additional repository types.

[1] <https://jupyter.org/hub>

[2] <https://researchdata.tuwien.ac.at>

[3] <https://www.ifs.tuwien.ac.at/infrastructures/dbrepo/>

[4] <https://jupyter.hpc.tuwien.ac.at/>

ID: 257 / DV03: 2

Developer Track

Topics: Research Transparency, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: FAIRness of repository resources, Signposting, Validation service, sustainable and machine-friendly scholarly web, HTTP Link Headers

The FAIR Signposting Validator

Martin Klein¹, James Powell¹, Herbert Van de Sompel²

¹Los Alamos National Laboratory, United States of America; ²Data Archiving and Networked Services

Increasing the level of FAIRness of resources is high on the agenda of repository developers and managers. The FAIR Signposting profile offers concrete recipes to approach this goal and has therefore seen an increased level of adoption in the international repository community. To further support developers, we have designed and implemented the FAIR Signposting Validator. The validator provides immediate feedback to users regarding the syntactic and semantic validity of their FAIR Signposting implementation. This presentation will outline the design, implementation details, and utility of the validator. We will share the source code openly for the developer community, in order to enable local installations.

ID: 277 / DV03: 3

Developer Track

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: hierarchical content; object-store, S3, complex-roles

Persisting complex, hierarchical repository content in an S3 object store

Paul Walk¹, Anusha Ranganathan²

¹Antleaf Ltd.; ²Cottage Labs

Antleaf and Cottage Labs are working with Ruhr University Bochum (RUB) to develop a Research Data Management System (RDMS) based on a Samvera Hyrax 3 repository. Three key requirements have, taken together, led to some interesting challenges:

1. RDMS must support multiple, complex data/metadata models
2. RDMS must preserve data privacy within each research group, until it is ready for publishing.
3. RDMS must persisting all data & metadata in RUB's S3 object storage facility

The presentation will give a brief overview of the three requirements, before describing the challenges that these requirements introduce both separately and in conjunction. It will then describe the technical solutions to these challenges, commenting on their effectiveness and any trade-offs that have had to be accommodated.

ID: 326 / DV03: 4

Developer Track

Topics: Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Digital preservation, Oxford Common File Layout (OCFL), Sustainable repositories, Fedora 6 Repository

The ORA Data Preservation Service – a lightweight, open-source, digital repository solution

Tom Wrobel

University of Oxford, United Kingdom

Digital preservation, and data preservation, are key concerns to repository owners and stakeholders. However, implementation of system-independent, versioned, digital storage for digital repository content is often proprietary and financially expensive. Here, we present an open source, decoupled, remote solution for the preservation of repository content in an OCFL (Oxford Common File Layout) file system using the Fedora 6 Repository application to manage ingest and export.

ID: 246 / DV03: 5

Developer Track

Topics: Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: FAIR; Interoperability; Signposting; Registries; Distributed Web; Next Generation Repositories

FAIRiCat: Supporting Discovery of a Repository's Interoperability Affordances

Herbert Van de Sompel¹, Martin Klein², Patrick Hochstenbach³

¹DANS, Austria; ²Los Alamos National Laboratory, USA; ³Ghent University, Belgium

A new effort under the "Signposting the Scholarly Web" umbrella specifies a way in which repositories can advertise the interoperability affordances they support by publishing a FAIR Interoperability Catalog, FAIRiCat in short. It also specifies how FAIRiCats can be discovered to support obtaining an insight in the nature of a repository's investments in interoperability, finding the machine entry points of repository-wide affordances (e.g. SPARQL endpoint), and examples of affordances that are available when interacting with individual objects managed by the repository (e.g. IIIF support).

09:00 - 10:30

Presentations: Trends and the Future of Open

Location: **Drottningporten 3**

Session Chair: **Lisa Lamont**, San Diego State University

ID: 375 / PR20: 1

Presentations

Topics: Repository Systems, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement

Keywords: European repositories, next generation repositories

Taking stock of the repository landscape in Europe: survey results and next steps

Kathleen Shearer¹, Eloy Rodrigues², Tamy Nakano¹, Natalia Manola², Martine Pronk³, Vanessa Proudman⁴

¹COAR, Canada; ²OpenAIRE, Greece; ³LIBER, The Netherlands; ⁴SPARC Europe, The Netherlands

Open Science is ushering in a new paradigm for research; one in which all researchers have unprecedented access to the full corpus of research for analysis, text and data mining, and other new research methods. A prerequisite for achieving this vision is a strong and well-functioning network of repositories that provides human and machine access to the wide range of valuable research outputs. In January 2023, OpenAIRE, LIBER, SPARC Europe, and COAR launched a joint strategy to strengthen the European repository network. As a first step, a survey was undertaken in February-March 2023.

The survey found that European repositories acquire, preserve and provide open access to tens or possibly hundreds of millions of valuable research outputs. They are used for sharing articles that may be paywalled in published journals, but also for providing access to a large variety of other types of research outputs including research data, theses/dissertations, conference papers, preprints, code, and so on. The survey has also exposed a number of important areas where the current repository landscape could be strengthened. This presentation will provide an overview of the results of the survey, and present the joint strategy being developed and deployed by our four organizations.

ID: 273 / PR20: 2

Presentations

Topics: Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Repository Systems, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals, EPrints, Visibility

Sustainable Development Goals in EPrints

Eleanor Dumbill, Will Fyson

CoSector, University of London, United Kingdom

Though there has been a great deal of attention given to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals since their introduction, the approach to recording research aligned with the goals in EPrints has been inconsistent and this has negatively impacted the visibility of such research. This presentation introduces a recently developed EPrints plugin for tracking and publicising research associated with the 17 SDGs. It will include a technical overview of this plugin and the features that have been developed to increase the transparency of SDG-related research in EPrints repositories.

ID: 370 / PR20: 3

Presentations

Topics: Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement, Metadata and Discoverability

Keywords: Interoperability guidelines, OpenAIRE, International alignment, metadata standards; harvesting

OpenAIRE guidelines streamlined, modernized and more global

Pedro Principe¹, André Vieira¹, Leonidas Pispiringas²

¹University of Minho, Portugal; ²OpenAIRE AMKE

The theme of this year's Open Repositories conference, focused on how we can benefit from repositories to empower global progress, drives us to present and discuss the future and new directions of the development of the OpenAIRE Interoperability Guidelines. This presentation aims to present and discuss the recent changes in the guidelines towards its simplification and harmonization, the open

	<p>issues reported by the community that need to be addressed by the working group and the main components that require a global synchronisation between regional and national repository networks and initiatives.</p> <p>The OpenAIRE Guidelines play a vital role in OpenAIRE's strategic approach to address the sustainability, openness, and modernization challenges faced by Scholarly Infrastructures, while ensuring enhanced interoperability.</p> <p>OpenAIRE Guidelines streamlined and modernized</p> <p>The OpenAIRE Guidelines are a suite of application profiles designed to allow research performing organisations to make their scholarly outputs visible through the OpenAIRE infrastructure. The profiles are based on established standards and designed to help repository managers expose publications, datasets and CRIS metadata via the OAI-PMH protocol. The OpenAIRE Guidelines have been released for publication repositories, data archives, CRIS systems, software repositories and repositories of other research products.</p> <hr/> <p>ID: 222 / PR20: 4 Presentations <i>Topics:</i> Research Transparency, Underrepresented Communities, Repository Systems, Research Data Management and Curation, Collaboration, Outreach and Engagement <i>Keywords:</i> Open Access Infrastructure, History of Open Access, Future of Open Access, Developer Perspectives</p> <p>Looking up from the weeds: seeing what's next for OA by learning from the past Richard David Jones Cottage Labs, United Kingdom</p> <p>This presentation looks at the history of Open Access from the perspective of the author, a software engineer in the sector for nearly 25 years. In that time he has been involved in local, national and international efforts in all aspects of the development of repositories and the infrastructure services that support them. It is about what we've actually seen be developed and become reality in that time, and how it connects to the goals and desires of the community. It asks what lessons we can learn from that time, and what that might tell us about the future of OA, and whether it is alive and well or under threat. What is the role that the repository has to play in the coming publishing paradigms which aim to improve global publishing equity (such as Diamond and Overlay Journals) and how can we as a community enable it.</p>
10:30 - 11:00	Coffee Break
11:00 - 11:50	<p>Keynote Speaker Dr. Monica Granados Location: Drottningporten</p> <p>Dr. Monica Granados has a PhD in ecology from McGill University. While working on her PhD, Monica discovered incentives in academia promote practices that make knowledge less accessible and has since devoted her career to working in the open science space in pursuit of making knowledge more equitable and accessible. She has worked on open... </p>
11:50 - 12:30	<p>Closing Plenary Location: Drottningporten Session Chair: Elizabeth Krznarich, DataCite</p>
12:30 - 13:30	Lunch